

OPEN ACCESS

Review—Electrolyte and Electrode Designs for Enhanced Ion Transport Properties to Enable High Performance Lithium Batteries

To cite this article: Buket Boz *et al* 2021 *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **168** 090501

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

The Electrochemical Society

Advancing solid state & electrochemical science & technology

242nd ECS Meeting

Oct 9 – 13, 2022 • Atlanta, GA, US

Abstract submission deadline: **April 8, 2022**

Connect. Engage. Champion. Empower. Accelerate.

MOVE SCIENCE FORWARD

Submit your abstract

Review—Electrolyte and Electrode Designs for Enhanced Ion Transport Properties to Enable High Performance Lithium Batteries

Buket Boz,^{1,2} Tanmay Dev,^{1,2} Alberto Salvadori,¹

¹Department of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, University of Brescia, Brescia 25123, Italy

²Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, University of Notre Dame, Notre Dame, Indiana 46556, United States of America

Lithium-ion batteries (LiBs) are recognized as the most rapidly growing energy storage technology. To improve the energy and power density of LiBs, tremendous progress has been made in every battery component. In this review, we focus on the investigations of electrolyte and electrode designs aimed at understanding and enhancing ion transport properties to improve the performance of LiBs. Theoretical, computational, and experimental studies of the importance of transport properties are highlighted, and the efforts to enhance the lithium transference number in organic electrolytes is discussed. We also review the significant ion transport challenges in porous electrodes and the demonstrated examples of advanced, high power/energy density electrodes. Overall, we focus on the most recent and pioneering works in terms of complex electrolytes with high transport properties and thick porous electrodes for high performance LiBs. This review intends to provide guidance for development of advanced electrolytes and electrodes for high performance LiBs through comprehensive compilation of prior understanding via experimental, computational, and theoretical points of view.

© 2021 The Author(s). Published on behalf of The Electrochemical Society by IOP Publishing Limited. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License (CC BY, <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse of the work in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. [DOI: 10.1149/1945-7111/ac1cc3]

Manuscript submitted June 24, 2021; revised manuscript received July 19, 2021. Published September 2, 2021.

The award of the 2019 Nobel Prize in Chemistry to Goodenough, Whittingham, and Yoshino highlights the importance of rechargeable lithium-ion battery (LiB) development on our world. Now more than ever before, high performance energy storage systems are sought for the storage of clean and renewably generated electricity and use of that electricity for a variety of applications. Higher power and energy densities, as well as lower costs, are desired for next generation battery systems to increase the electrification of transportation.

The electrochemically active portion of the conventional LiB consists of the positive and negative electrodes, liquid electrolyte, and the separator, a porous material used to allow ion transport through the liquid electrolyte while maintaining electronic insulation between the two electrodes. A typical electrolyte for LiBs consists of a binary lithium salt and additives dissolved in a solvent mixture based on organic carbonates.¹ The distinctive features of commercial liquid electrolytes are relatively high ionic conductivity (1–10 mS cm⁻¹) at room temperature, easy processibility, and good electrode wettability. However, a majority fraction of the total ionic conductivity is due to the anion motion. As a result, a concentration gradient forms in the electrolyte in the presence of an electric field. The formation of the ion concentration gradient limits the practical charge/discharge rates as well as the active material utilization, particularly for thick, porous electrodes.

Here, we review the state of knowledge regarding electrolyte and electrode designs for enhanced ion transport properties with the goal of mitigating the aforementioned limitations in charge/discharge rates and active material utilization in LiBs. First, we will briefly describe the relevant electrochemical transport theory and continuum modeling efforts to describe ion transport effects on LiBs. Next, the experimental progress in the development of organic electrolytes with enhanced ion transport properties and incorporation of these into LiBs is described. Third, the challenges regarding ion transport in porous electrodes as investigated from theoretical, simulation, and experimental perspectives are discussed. Finally, we end with a review of experimental efforts in electrode design to alleviate the ion transport limitations.

Electrochemical Transport Theory and Continuum Modelling

Computational modelling and simulations provide tools to comprehend concurrent microscopic processes and to predict the response of electrochemical systems in a wide range of timescales and lengths. Several modelling strategies can be tailored to capture specific features of complex battery systems. For instance, density functional theory (DFT) calculations and molecular dynamics (MD) are being used to investigate ionic interactions at the electrode/electrolyte interfaces at the atomistic scale. In terms of understanding the ion transport mechanisms and ionic speciation within electrolytes, *atomistic scale modelling* is important; we refer the reader to excellent summaries of this area which fall out of the scope of this review and studies.^{2–5}

Continuum models.—Continuum models correspond well to predict macroscopic quantities of interest, such as cycling efficiency, electrode utilization and power capability or the evolution of mechanical stresses, degradation. This class of models has been applied to heuristic (equivalent circuit) models, capable of phenomenologically fitting the voltage response of batteries, as well as to microscale computations, in which the real geometry of the porous electrode is reconstructed from X-ray tomography.^{6–9}

In 2020, Li and Monroe reviewed continuum multiscale frameworks for lithium ion batteries, coupling nanoscale and macroscale approaches into thermodynamically rigorous multiphysics models.¹⁰ Another comprehensive review of computational modeling for Li-ion batteries, including macroscopic, microscopic and multiscale strategies was published by Grazioli and colleagues.¹¹

This section deals with continuum models and experimental studies applied to LiBs with different types of *organic electrolytes*, with the goal of understanding the impacts of ion transport properties on battery performance. The most widespread LiB model was developed by Newman and co-workers, considering the electrolyte as first as a dilute solution, later on extended to moderately diluted solutions. Lastly, the most advanced model was formulated within the concentrated solution theory, and it is still widely applied for continuum LiB modeling.^{12–15}

Brief summary on electrochemical transport theory.—In any phase of a battery, the system consists of ionic species or chemically distinct molecules. The concentration of species c_k and velocity of species \vec{v}_k form the molar flux, $\vec{N}_k = c_k \vec{v}_k$.

*Electrochemical Society Member.

²E-mail: jennifer.l.schaefer.43@nd.edu

The flux density of each dissolved species is given by the Nernst-Planck constitutive prescription,¹⁶

$$\vec{N}_k = \underbrace{-z_k u_k F c_k \nabla \phi}_{\text{Migration}} - \underbrace{D_k \nabla c_k}_{\text{Diffusion}} + \underbrace{c_k \vec{v}_k}_{\text{Convection}} \quad [\text{molcm}^{-2}] \quad [1]$$

In Eq. 1, the dragging movement of species is all due to the motion of the fluid with the bulk velocity \vec{v}_k . In the presence of an electric field ($-\nabla\phi$), the motion is driven by the migration ($z_k u_k$ number of charges carried by ions and ion mobility respectively). Species' Brownian motion is driven by concentration gradients, ∇c_k , captured by the species diffusion (D_k diffusion coefficient).

Charge per mole on a species is defined as $z_k F$, where z_k is the species' charge and F is the Faraday constant. The current density in an electrolytic solution (i.e. the motion of charged species) is related to their flux density \vec{N}_k by Faraday's law of electrolysis,

$$\vec{i} = F \sum_k z_k N_k \quad [\text{A cm}^{-2}] \quad [2]$$

Mass balance for every species can be written as,

$$\frac{\partial c_k}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot \vec{N}_k, \quad [3]$$

with \vec{N}_k as it was stated in (1). The excess charge density (ρ_e) produces the mean electric field (\vec{E}), which obeys Gauss's law.

$$\nabla \cdot (\epsilon \vec{E}) = \rho_e \quad [4]$$

where ϵ is the permittivity.

Nernst-Planck dilute solution theory (1) is the simplest model, ignoring finite volume occupied by the salt and any interaction between solute species.¹⁷ Newman's concentrated solution theory is able to capture more profoundly the reality of ionic interactions.¹² In a conventional electrolyte solution, one should take into consideration the conductance of multiple species. A simple binary electrolyte consisted of a solvent ($\kappa = 0$, $z_0 = 0$) and full dissociated salt with cations and anions ($\kappa = +$, $\kappa = -$). The salt satisfies $\nu_+ z_+ + \nu_- z_- = 0$, where ν is the velocity of the ions. The local electroneutrality in terms of concentration of the species is written as $z_+ c_+ = z_- c_-$. The salt chemical potential (μ_e) can be written as $\mu_e = \nu_+ \mu_+ + \nu_- \mu_-$. If the solvent velocity v_0 is chosen as the reference velocity, the flux for cations is written as

$$\vec{N}_+ = -\frac{\nu_+ D_{CT}}{\nu RT c_0} c \nabla \mu_e + \frac{t_+^0 \vec{i}}{F z_+} + c_0 \vec{v}_0 \quad [5]$$

Where t_+^0 is cation transference number reference to the solvent and \mathcal{D} is the thermodynamic diffusivity.

As clearly seen from the Eq. 5, two transport properties play a crucial role in ionic motion, the cation transference number and ionic conductivity. Li^+ transference number in a binary salt electrolyte relates the diffusivity of Li^+ and its counteranion.¹²

$$t_+ = \frac{z_+ \mathcal{D}_+}{z_+ \mathcal{D}_+ + z_- \mathcal{D}_-} \quad [6]$$

$$t_{\text{Li}^+} = \frac{D_{\text{Li}^+}}{D_{\text{Li}^+} + D_-} \quad [7]$$

Regarding Eq. 7, transference number is also simply the fraction of total ionic conductivity which is carried by Li^+ in conventional liquid electrolyte. The reader is referred to a textbook by Newman and Balsara for a more complete description of the nuances of the

transference numbers in terms of reference frame (e.g., t_+ vs t_+^0 , and the complications introduced by concentrated solutions).¹⁸

Ionic conductivity can generally be described by

$$\sigma_{\text{total}} = \sum n_j q_j \mu_j \quad [8]$$

Where n_j , q_j and μ_j represent the number of ions of type j in the material, the charge of the ion of type j , and the mobility of the ion of type j , respectively. The total ionic conductivity is the sum of the products of the terms in Eq. 8, for all effective mobile ion species in the electrolyte, and it is readily measured experimentally.

The cation transference number in binary electrolyte systems turns out to be considerably lower than unity, typically 0.3 to 0.4. As a main consequence, during battery operation anions tend to migrate in the opposite direction of lithium ions and to accumulate at the electrode surface. The lower the transference number the more severe concentration gradient occurs in the electrolyte, limiting the battery charge/discharge rate. In turn, a concentration overpotential results that restricts the operating voltage of the cell. Therefore, the battery exhibits limited energy and power density.

In 1994, the importance of lithium transference number, t_{Li^+} , on lithium battery performance was highlighted by Newman and coworkers in a numerical study based on concentrated solution theory.¹³ The cell response for two different scenarios, 1) t_{Li^+} of unity and decreasing the ionic conductivity ten-fold (Figs. 1b and 2) $t_{\text{Li}^+} = 0.3$ and high conductivity (Fig. 1c), were compared. Unity t_{Li^+} with low conductivity was predicted to be more favorable, with higher discharge potentials and capacities achieved. Additionally, it was shown that high transference number does not have an impact on the system when operating at very low discharge rates, since the concentration gradient is not large enough to cause the depletion of electrolyte; on the contrary, at high rates the improvement is significant. It is concluded that even with a decrease in the total ionic conductivity, unity transference number improves the battery performance, especially at high discharge rates. Since this seminal work, the field has recognized the importance of transport properties on system performance and efforts including electrochemical transport modeling and experimental investigations have continued.

In 2017, McCloskey and coworkers highlighted the importance of high transference number especially with high C-rate applications such as electric vehicles (during acceleration) by using Newman's one dimensional (1D) battery model as it is shown in Fig. 2.¹⁹ A simple 1D model was developed based on the conventional lithium ion battery configuration, a porous lithium graphite and lithium cobalt oxide $\text{LiC}_6/\text{separator}/\text{LiCoO}_2$ with varying conductivity and transference number 1–10 mS cm^{-1} , 0.40 and 0.70, respectively. Taking into consideration the trade-off between conductivity and transference number, the outcomes were compared with the conventional LiB with liquid electrolyte lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF_6). The impact of high transference number on state of charge was more substantial at higher current densities. For instance, at 2 C, 0.8 transference number with 50% lower conductivity of conventional liquid system had resulted in the same performance of conventional liquid electrolyte. Therefore, it was pointed out the importance of t_{Li^+} as well as high ionic conductivity. Beside the simulations, this paper provides an excellent review on how to tailor polymer electrolytes to enhanced transport property polymer electrolytes.

The Newman concentrated solution theory electrochemical model is also used for LiBs with polymer electrolytes with some modifications to evaluate the transport properties of the electrolyte and the battery performance. In 2001, Georén and Lindbergh published an innovative study on solid polymer electrolytes (SPEs) by numerical and experimental approaches.²¹ A continuum model using the concentrated solution theory was implemented to determine transport properties and thermodynamic activity factor with the

Figure 1. Summary of Newman's and coworkers' study on the importance of transference number. (a) the predicted effect of small variations of transference number on ion concentration profiles with galvanostatic operation (D ; diffusion coefficient, t_{\pm} ; transference number). (b) the predicted potential profiles with unity transference number at different current densities (I ; current density, κ ionic conductivity (S cm⁻¹)). (c) the predicted potential profiles with one-fifth of the conductivity and lithium transference number of 0.3. Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Ref. 13.

Figure 2. McCloskey and coworker's model based on Newman's model. The impact of various transference number and ionic conductivity effect on concentration gradient. Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Ref. 19 Copyright (2017) American Chemical Society.

concentration-dependent parameters of the chosen electrolytes, copolymers of ethylene and propylene oxide with 0.1 and 2 M lithium bis (trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (LiTFSI) salt. The characterization of the SPE was conducted experimentally and the numerical model was employed by using the experimentally obtained transport properties rigorously. This approach targeted to minimize the issues associated with concentration variations during the experiments to measure the transport properties. Overall, the numerical model was useful to test different theoretical cases; ideal vs non-ideal electrolyte and locally constant properties vs concentration-dependent parameters.

In 2018, the Srinivasan and Balsara groups reported a predictive model with concentrated solution theory for symmetric lithium polymer cells to compare cycling characteristics.²² A well-studied polymer/lithium salt system, polyethylene oxide (PEO) and lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide (LiTFSI), was chosen to investigate salt concentration and potential profiles in symmetric lithium-polymer-lithium cells. The validity of the model was tested by comparison with the experimental cycling performance and it was concluded that the model and the experiments were in perfect agreement. The model can be used to predict the performance behavior of polymer electrolyte systems with known transport properties.

Another important study on polymer electrolytes by means of continuum modeling and experimental work was reported by the Srinivasan group in 2014.²³ For the cathode active layer, lithium iron phosphate (LiFePO_4) particles were blended with poly(3-hexylthiophene)-b-poly(ethylene oxide) (P3HT-PEO) copolymer and LiTFSI lithium salt. For the separator, poly(styrene)-b-poly(ethylene oxide) (PS-PEO) copolymer with LiTFSI was used for both experimental set-up and modelling. This model predicts the limiting factors of all type of SPEs which can be also adapted to different type of polymer electrolyte applications such gel polymer electrolytes. The mathematical model was based on Newman and co-workers' macro-homogeneous battery model considering concentrated solution theory. Ionic transport in copolymer binder and electrolyte were treated as in the solution phase of a porous electrode. The main outcome of this study is the understanding of the impact of potential-dependent electronic conductivity in the cathode on the rate performance in the all-solid battery.

In 2019, Balsara and coworkers used the concentrated solution theory to predict theoretical potential and salt concentration profiles as a function of position in the cell.²⁴ The model prediction and experimental measurements were in the agreement in terms of limiting current results. The Balsara and Srinivasan research groups compared the experimentally determined limiting current up to the solubility limit of the electrolyte with predictions from Newman's concentrated solution theory.²⁵

At this point, we can say that the determination of transport properties is highly crucial especially in polymer/liquid electrolyte complex systems. Regarding Newman's model, to describe the bulk ionic transport in complex electrolyte systems, knowledge of the conductivity as well as the diffusion coefficients of the ionic species in solution ($D_{+/-}$), transference number (t_+^0), and the mean molar activity coefficient ($\gamma_{+/-}$) are required to describe ion transport. The concentrated solution theory is preferred in modelling investigations of complex electrolyte systems since it allows the researchers to use experimentally obtained transport properties in which a quantitative comparison between experiments and models can be accomplished towards to reliable predictive capabilities.

Experimental studies of ion transport parameters.—Experimental studies of ion transport parameters have been designed to validate models and to feed them with appropriate transport properties, towards using numerical tools to optimize battery response.^{26–28} Over the years, Lindberg and colleagues have contributed to the field by using concentrated solution theory and directly fitting numerical solutions of transport simulations to the current/voltage relationships measured during electrochemical experiments.^{26,29,30}

In 2005, Valøen and Reimers studied the diffusion coefficient, transference number and salt activity of lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF_6) in propylene carbonate/ethylene carbonate/dimethyl carbonate (PC/EC/DMC) at different temperatures and salt concentrations (7.7×10^{-6} to 3.9 M).³¹ Experiments suggested that Li^+ transference number did not vary significantly with the concentration, whereas diffusion coefficient and salt activity parameters were highly dependent on the temperature and concentration of the electrolyte. Cell performance was found to be a function of temperature, especially at high currents when the strong concentration gradient and increased heat production challenged realistic predictions. In 2017, Ehrl and colleagues published two studies on determination of transport properties of lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4) in EC/DEC (ethylene carbonate-diethyl carbonate) solvent mixture.^{32,33} The second part of the study focused on determining transference number in liquid binary electrolytes with LiClO_4 with different concentrations (0.01 to 2 M) in (EC-DEC 50:50 % weight). A novel approach was proposed to determine the transference number based on the concentration cells experiments by taking into account the direct determination of thermodynamic factor introduced by Landesfeind³⁴ and colleagues. The measured and calculated transference number were found to be in agreement. It was suggested that the novel approach was much more precise to determine transference number in concentrated binary electrolyte solutions rather than the conventional potentiostatic polarization method.

In regards to in-situ characterization methods, Krachkovskiy's group used a combination of in-situ 1D ^7Li NMR imaging and slice-selective NMR to determine ion diffusivity of a conventional liquid electrolyte (1 M LiTFSI/Propylene Carbonate).³⁵ Krachkovskiy's group combined of in-situ MRI and inverse mathematical modeling to determine spatially dependent ion diffusion coefficients and transference numbers.^{36,37} Lindbergh and Furó groups utilized in situ ^7Li NMR imaging to observe the development of the concentration gradient in the liquid electrolyte of Li-ion batteries during operation and to assess the mass transport properties.³⁸

It is noted that the accurate measurement of transference numbers has been a debated topic for over three decades. More recently, the notion of negative transference number due to ion clustering, became a debated research topic both experimentally and theoretically.^{39,20} Electrophoretic NMR (eNMR) is a powerful tool to determine the velocities of the ions under applied electric fields. Schönhoff and coworkers applied the eNMR technique to show that Li^+ drifts toward the positive electrode in complex ion clusters in lithium salt/ionic liquid mixtures at certain concentration and time ranges.³⁹ Balsara and Srinivasan have recently theoretically considered the negative transference number with poly(ethylene oxide)-based (PEO) and lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide (LiTFSI) electrolytes.^{20,40} Based on Newman's concentrated

Figure 3. Kim and coworkers illustrated the cation, anion, and ionic cluster motion in a PEO/LiTFSI electrolyte. The orange line shows the occurrence of concentration gradient. Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Ref. 20.

solution theory, the effects of diffusion and migration driving forces on ion motion were examined. The negative transference number was predicted at short times in regions far from the electrode surface where Li^+ moves in the same direction of TFSI^- when contained within a negatively charged ion cluster, such as $[\text{LiTFSI}_2]^-$, as illustrated in Fig. 3. Thus, in this region, majority of the current is predicted to be carried by the anions to compensate negative contribution of Li^+ moving in the wrong direction. The drift of these ion clusters should be compensated by diffusive mass transport of neutral or Li ion aggregates.

Most recently, *operando* X-ray photon correlation spectroscopy and X-ray absorption microscopy were used in tandem with concentrated solution theory and molecular dynamics simulations to investigate ion transport in PEO-LiTFSI electrolytes; in contrast with some of the aforementioned studies, a fairly concentration-independent lithium transference number of about 0.2 was suggested.⁴¹ These results are similar to what is obtained using the popular electrochemical Bruce Vincent method,⁴² via pulse-field gradient nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy,^{43,44} and via e-NMR when a model-free approach⁴⁵ is used for the data interpretation. Importantly, this work demonstrated “the first spatially resolved direct measurements of ion velocities as a function of time in an electrochemical system,” input of those experimentally determined transport values into concentrated solution theory models, quantification of transport parameters such as the transference number, and insight from atomic scale simulations on the origins of the observed results. This work is anticipated to be authoritative for the field, and it lends some confidence to the many experimental transference number measurements performed via the Bruce Vincent method that are reported in the literature.

Single ion conducting polymer electrolytes (SIPES).—Single ion conducting polymer electrolytes by definition have cation transference number of unity. In SIPES, the counterions are firmly held by covalent tethering to the polymer matrix and do not translationally diffuse. Considering charge neutrality in the electrolyte, the concentration of lithium ions in the electrolyte even in the presence of an electric field is uniform throughout the interelectrode distance, matching that of the immobile counterions. SIPES are considered promising, and there have been ongoing efforts to improve them for decades.^{46–48} However at room temperature, the ionic conductivity of this type of materials is not high enough for many applications. Introducing solvent to the polymer network increases the ionic conductivity. Compared to the large body of experimental works, only a few reported studies with mathematical modelling of SIPES were published.

In 2018, Krewer's group implemented a pseudo-two-dimensional (P2D) model to compare the responses of batteries based on SIPES

and conventional binary liquid electrolytes.⁴⁹ The continuum model was based on Newman's model with addition of double layer capacitance.⁵⁰ At higher rates, it was reported that the potential losses in the electrolyte region improved with use of the SIPE, which led to higher energy in comparison to the liquid electrolyte case. In addition, the effect of the electrode thickness was investigated and SIPEs were predicted to be suitable for thicker electrode designs. An elementary 1-dimensional model for a solid state lithium-ion battery with a single ion conductor electrolyte and a lithium metal negative electrode was proposed by McMeeking's group.⁵¹

Extension to multiscale modeling.—Multiscale modeling aims to provide a bridge between micro to macro scale. However, the main limitation of application of Newman's models to multiscale modeling stands in one of the major assumptions, electroneutrality. This condition is met in reality and well adapted in all models, yet replacing Maxwell's equations with electroneutrality prevents conserving energy in scale transitions, a cornerstone condition in multiscale modeling. In 2015, Salvadori and coworkers developed a novel approach for continuum ionic transport modeling of liquid electrolyte for lithium ion battery systems which is multiscale compatible.⁵² This model directly allows the writing of scale transition equations stemming from the electrostatic form of Maxwell's equations. In 2019, Franco and coworkers published a comprehensive review on multiscale modelling.⁵³ The authors reviewed different types of multiscale modelling approaches, tools, and outcomes.

A link between Newman's and multiphysics models that emanate from non-equilibrium thermodynamics of continuum were studied, with specific reference on the notion of the transference number.⁵⁴ Danilov and colleagues proposed innovative models of solid state lithium ion battery.⁵⁵ The model consisted of the charge transfer kinetics at the electrode and electrolyte interface, diffusion of lithium ions, and migration in the electrolyte under different operating conditions. It was declared that the transport limitation in solid state electrolytes was related to the overpotential. The impact was much clearer with high current densities.

Grazioli and coworkers reported a solid state polymer electrolyte model with a coupled ionic conduction and deformation model to enquire about the mechanical stress caused by ions' movement.⁵⁶ The model investigates the effect of polymer stiffness, thickness of SPE, and internally induced stress under the battery operation. With regard to SPE modeling, the model is similar to Danilov's model. Landstorfer and coworkers formulated a mathematical model for ion flux in solid electrolytes, rigorously derived from non-equilibrium thermodynamics, allowing the computation of the ion concentration at the electrode/electrolyte interface.⁵⁷

In 2019, Zhao and colleagues published an extensive review on modelling of electro-chemo-mechanics in lithium ion batteries which includes solid electrolytes.⁵⁸

Organic-Based Electrolytes with Enhanced Transport Properties

The desire for high transference number (t_{Li^+}) and high conductivity have become the motivation for new design of electrolytes. Immobilizing the anions in a polymer backbone is one of the ways to mitigate anion diffusion and cause high t_{Li^+} . With dry solid single ion conducting polymer electrolytes, high t_{Li^+} can be fulfilled, but these systems have shown to possess lower ionic conductivity.⁵⁹

Besides from the organic based polymer electrolytes, there is a whole literature body on lithium inorganic electrolytes that are single ion conducting in nature.^{60–62} To keep the limited focus of the review, only organic-based electrolytes with high t_{Li^+} are discussed here. Organic electrolytes are thought to be advantageous to inorganic electrolytes on the basis of low density, flexibility, and potential greater sustainability.

Figure 4. The discharge capacities at different C-rates and temperatures (red and blue lines for SIPE BAB triblock copolymers, black line for P(EO)₂₀LiClO₄ + 5% S-ZrO₂ electrolyte⁶⁵). Reprinted from Ref. 64 with permission from Nature Publishing Group, copyright 2013.

All-solid-state high transference number polymer electrolytes.—The chemistry and material properties of single-ion conducting polymer electrolytes (SIPEs) have recently been reviewed by Armand and colleagues.⁶³ Here, we focus on the most outstanding examples and application of SIPEs and other high transference number all-solid-state polymer electrolytes in LiBs.

In 2013, Bouchet and Armand's group reported on a promising liquid-free SIPE, triblock copolymer polyanionic lithium 4-styrenesulphonyl(trifluoromethylsulphonyl)-poly (ethylene oxide) imide (P(STFSILi)-b-PEO-b-P(STFSILi)), for lithium battery applications.⁶⁴ In this paper, the lithium ionomer PSTFSILi was block copolymerized, rather than blended, with PEO to create a high performing single-ion BAB triblock copolymer electrolyte. At 60°C, ionic conductivity was measured at 1.3×10^{-5} S cm⁻¹, relatively high for an all-solid SIPE, and the transference number of 0.85 was measured via electrochemical methods. The characterized solid polymer electrolytes (SPEs) were assembled for a full cell cycling test to confirm their usefulness in the Li/LiFePO₄ configuration. At different temperatures (60°C, 70°C and 80°C) and rates, the battery showed an impressive performance for approximately 80 cycles without capacity fading. As it is shown in Fig. 4, at 80°C and 2 C, the discharge capacity was obtained as 138 mAh g⁻¹, much unlike the capacity of lithium metal batteries with dry polymer electrolyte reported in the literature for a comparable cell employing the conventional lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide (LiTFSI) + PEO polymer electrolyte. This work is one of the milestone experimental studies on SIPEs with enhanced transport properties.

In 2016, Ma and colleagues reported an all-solid SIPE composed of a polyanionic lithium salt, poly[(4-styrenesulfonyl) (trifluoromethyl(S- trifluoromethyl sulfonylimino) sulfonyl)imide] (PSsTFSI⁻) mixed with high-molecular-weight poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO).⁶⁶ The bound anionic groups on this polyanion have less binding energy to Li⁺ than the PSTFSI. At 90°C ionic conductivity was 1.35×10^{-4} S cm⁻¹ and the transference number was akin to unity, 0.91. This electrolyte is one of the highest performing SIPEs reported in the literature. However, this study consists of only the synthesizing and the characterization of SIPE. The full cell cycling was not performed. The complex synthetic procedure to obtain the polyanion likely limits the practicality of this electrolyte.

In 2017, Armand and coworkers reported a novel dry SIPE with lithium poly[(trifluoromethyl)sulfonyl acrylamide (PA-LiTFSI)] blended with PEO.⁶⁷ At 80 °C, ionic conductivity was measured as 1.77×10^{-5} S cm⁻¹. Transference number was measured as only 0.68 which was explained by the authors as, even though anions were attached to polymer backbone, some ionic impurities were

present in the electrolyte. Besides, accurate electrochemical transference number measurements have been considered challenging as results may be impacted by interfacial chemistry.⁶⁸ A Li/PA-LiTFSI/LiFePO₄ cell achieved 125–140 mAh g⁻¹ over 5 cycles at 80°C and C/20. The overpotential between charging and discharge potentials was extremely high, which displays the high resistivity of electrolyte and unstable solid electrolyte interface (SEI). Thus, the cell failed abruptly.

A solid-state polymer electrolyte with high t_{Li+} containing dissolved lithium salt was reported by Hsu and colleagues in 2020.⁶⁹ A network of poly(ethylene oxide-co-polypropylene oxide) (PEO-co-PO) with cage-like polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxane (POSS) junctions was used with lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide (LiTFSI) salt. It was reported that POSS improved the dissociation of LiTFSI by interacting with the TFSI⁻ anions resulting in a transference number of 0.63 and room temperature ionic conductivity of 1.1 × 10⁻⁴ S cm⁻¹. The full cycling and rate capability were also tested for the SPE with the Li/SPE/LiFePO₄ configuration. At 1 C, the discharge capacity was noted as 137 mAh g⁻¹ at room temperature. In comparison to previous SPE examples, it is an encouraging result.

One of the novel and recent studies on dry SIPEs was reported by Yuan and coworkers.⁷⁰ Lithium poly [(cyano)(4-styrenesulfonyl) imide] (LiPCSI) blended with (PEO) was proposed as a solid polymer electrolyte for LIBs with various ether oxygen (EO)/Li⁺ charge ratio. The highest ionic conductivity and transference number were obtained with PEO₈-LiPCSI 7.33 × 10⁻⁵ S cm⁻¹ at 60 °C and 0.84 respectively. Full cycling performance was reported with the Li/PEO₈-LiPCSI/LiFePO₄ configuration. The cell maintained almost 100% capacity after the first couple cycles. The discharge capacity at 0.1 C retained after 80 cycles was 120 mAh g⁻¹. As a sign of low electrochemical stability, the overpotential increased from 0.06 V to 0.1 V over the 80 cycles. In comparison, use of polyethylene oxide—lithium perchlorate (PEO₈-LiClO₄) with equivalent conditions resulted in capacity fading and failure after the 12th cycle.

Li-conducting inorganic - polymer composite electrolytes.—

Composite polymer electrolytes wherein lithium-conducting inorganic electrolytes are mixed with polymer electrolytes are a growing area of research.^{71–73} Li₇La₃Zr₂O₁₂ (LLZO),^{74–76} lithium thiophosphate glasses,⁷⁷ Li₂S–P₂S₅ and NASICON type conductors are some of the inorganic components that have been well-studied.⁷⁸ Simultaneous high transference number, ionic conductivity, flexibility, and processability are proposed to be achievable, and thus composite polymer electrolytes are considered one of the most promising solid electrolyte candidate for LIBs.^{79–83}

In 2020, Cai and colleagues reported a composite solid-state polymer electrolyte which consisted of a three dimensional Li_{6.4}La₃Zr₂Al_{0.2}O₁₂ (3D LLZAO) framework infilled with conventional PEO/LiTFSI (T-LAPL).⁸⁴ Ionic conductivity and t_{Li+} were measured at room temperature as 2.51 × 10⁻⁴ S cm⁻¹ and 0.53 respectively. This ceramic blended electrolyte showed promising cycling performance with the Li/T-LAPL/LiFePO₄ cell configuration with initial discharge capacity of 165.9 mAh g⁻¹ at 0.2 C and 80 % capacity retention after 100 cycles. A PEO/LLZTO composite electrolyte was investigated at different operating conditions by Zhang and coworkers.⁸⁵ Goodenough and colleagues have also made substantial efforts on composite polymer electrolyte for LIBs.^{86–88} The chemical composition and processing of the composite polymer electrolytes determine the predominant Li⁺ and anion transport pathways: through the inorganic particles, the organic bulk matrix, or at the inorganic-organic interfaces.

Single-ion conducting gel polymer electrolytes.—All-solid organic-based electrolytes generally have lower ionic conductivity than liquids and some inorganic electrolytes and therefore are required to be operated at high temperatures to achieve relevant charge/discharge rates for LIBs. Single ion conducting gel polymer

electrolytes (SIPEs) already address high transference number by immobilizing the anions into the polymer backbone. Confining liquid plasticizer such as solvents or liquid electrolyte into the polymer network to make a gel polymer electrolyte (GPE) can allow for increased ionic conductivity. Safety issues in terms of flammability and leakage that are associated with liquid electrolytes may still exist, but some studies suggest that the overall safety can be improved by decreasing the amount of solvent.^{89,90} The specific solvents and polymers used will also impact the electrochemical stability and compatibility with various full cell configurations. Etheral solvents have excellent reductive stability and may be preferred for use with Li metal anodes. Organic carbonate solvents, in contrast, have higher oxidative stability making them more potentially useful for high voltage cells and have higher dielectric constants that often allow for enhanced ion pair dissociation and ionic conductivity.

Mixing polyanions with solvents can yield high transference number electrolytes with much improved ionic conductivity at room temperature. In 2016 and 2018, Oh and colleagues and Nguyen and coworkers reported two different gel SIPEs swollen in carbonate solutions in which the electrolyte exhibited 10⁻³ S cm⁻¹ ionic conductivity at room temperature.^{91,92} Nguyen and colleagues synthesized a nanostructured SIPE based on a multi-block copoly (arylene ether sulfone) bearing lithium perfluorosulfonamide functional groups.⁹¹ The SIPE doped with ethylene carbonate (EC) displayed excellent electrochemical stability and cycling performance in both Li/Li[Ni_{1/3}Co_{1/3}Mn_{1/3}]O₂ and Li/LiFePO₄ cell configurations. This remarkable study is considered a milestone for high performance LiBs with SIPEs.

In 2019, Borzutki and colleagues reported a gel SIPE based on a homopolymer containing polysulfonamide moieties at the backbone. In propylene carbonate (PC) and EC solvent mixture, the gel SIPE has an ionic conductivity of 5 × 10⁻⁴ S cm⁻¹ at 20 °C.⁹³ Porcarelli and colleagues reported a crosslinked gel SIPE containing functionalized poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) chains copolymerized with lithium 1-[3-(methacryloyloxy)-propylsulfonyl]-1-(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (LiMTFSI) monomer.⁹⁴ At room temperature, the SIPE showed an outstanding ionic conductivity 10⁻⁴ S cm⁻¹ and 0.86 transference number when gelled with PC solvent. In 2020, the Bresser group reported multi-block co-poly(arylene ether sulfone)-based gel SIPEs with PC solvent with an ionic conductivity of 0.6 mS cm⁻¹ at 20°C.⁹⁵

In 2020, Schaefer and colleagues reported on crosslinked single-ion conducting gel polymer electrolytes prepared simply by copolymerization of difunctionalized oligomeric macromonomers with ionic monomer STFSI, ion exchange, and swelling in solvent.⁹⁶ Crosslinked SIPE gel electrolyte based on poly(tetrahydrofuran) (PTHF) diacrylate and STFSI was compared to the analogous PEG diacrylate based gel electrolyte. Much improved room temperature ionic conductivities were acquired for the PTHF-based gel SIPEs upon swelling in 1,3-dioxolane/dimethoxyethane (DOL/DME), 2.7 × 10⁻⁵ S cm⁻¹, and in ethylene carbonate and diethyl carbonate (EC/DEC), 1.2 × 10⁻⁴ S cm⁻¹, compared with the PEG SIPEs. Despite the incompatibility of EC/DEC solvent mixture and lithium metal, the swelled PTHF SIPE thick membrane (165 μm) achieved a limiting current density of 1 mA cm⁻².

Different types of single ion conducting polymers have been developing to enhance the high transport properties. In 2017, Deng and colleagues studied a gel SIPE based on a sp³ boron network which was synthesized by coupling of lithium bis(allylmalonate) borate (LiBAMB) and pentaerythritol tetrakis(2-mercaptoacetate) (PETMP) via a one-step photoinitiated *in situ* thiol-ene click reaction in plasticizers.⁹⁷ At 25 °C, 1.47 × 10⁻³ S cm⁻¹ ionic conductivity was achieved in 85% gamma-butyrolactone (GBL). The lithium transference number was close to unity at 0.89. Above all, the full cell cycling of Li/SIPE/LiFePO₄ delivered 124 mAh g⁻¹ capacity with 1 C after 500 cycles.

Figure 5. Zhang and colleagues' study on SIPE full cell cycling performance with Li/LiFePO₄. (a) the C-rate test. (b) The discharge capacities at different C-rates. (c) The Coulombic efficiency for 400 cycles. Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Ref. 98.

In 2019, Zhang and colleagues investigated polymer matrixes based on backbone pentaerythritol tetrakis (2-mercaptoacetate) (PTMP) and pentaerythritol tetraacrylate (PETA) with STFSI ionic monomer.⁹⁸ The difference from the previous studies was that the SIPEs were not self-standing but instead polymers were crosslinked on a supporting layer, polypropylene (PP) nonwoven fabric. The ionic conductivity at room temperature in the solvent mixture of ethylene carbonate-dimethylene carbonate (EC/DMC) was 8.4×10^{-4} S cm⁻¹, and the transference number was measured at 0.93. Li/LiFePO₄ cycling results are shown in Figure 5. Li/LiFePO₄ cells with this gel SIPE showed an excellent performance with 83% capacity retention after 400 cycles at 0.1 mA cm⁻². The

performance was compared with a liquid electrolyte under the same conditions which resulted in 50% better capacity for 400 cycles.

High transference number gel polymer electrolytes with free salt.—To overcome the low ionic conductivity problem associated with tethering of the anion to the polymer backbone, another solution is to confine a liquid electrolyte with dissolved salt into a specially designed polymer matrix to yield a system with enhanced transport properties. Figures 6 and 7 illustrate the results some of the high performance GPEs for various LiB configurations. Only a few studies of this type have been reported exhibiting high t_{Li+} , high ionic conductivity, and cycling stability.

The Archer group reported one of the most compelling free salt containing GPEs in the literature with 1.14×10^{-3} S cm⁻¹ at 20 °C and exceedingly high t_{Li+} . The membrane was composed of a porous, crosslinked PEG network with tethered lithiated sulfonate (-SO₃Li) immersed in the common 1 M LiTFSI (DOL/DME) liquid electrolyte.¹⁰¹ t_{Li+} of the system is reported as an impressive 0.96, which may be the highest transference number ever reported for a gel electrolyte containing free salt.⁹⁹ The high performance porous membrane was utilized in the Li/Sulfur (S) configuration. The Coulombic efficiency of the cell was obtained as 98% for more than 100 cycles without lithium nitrate additive, which suggests that the membrane was effective at rejecting polysulfide anions produced in the cathode during discharge.

Following this, Wang and colleagues reported a polyethylene-supported gel polymer electrolyte based on poly(ethylene glycol) dimethacrylate (PEGDMA) crosslinked with sulfonate monomer in conjunction with 1 M lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF₆) ethylene carbonate, ethyl methyl carbonate, and diethyl carbonate (EC/EMC/DEC) liquid electrolyte, which had an ionic conductivity of 4.5×10^{-4} S cm⁻¹ at room temperature with 0.72 t_{Li+} .¹⁰⁰ In conjunction with comparatively high transport properties, cycling performance for Li/GPE/LiFePO₄ was improved significantly with this electrolyte compared to the pure liquid electrolyte. The GPE was able to cycle at 5 C whereas, the cell with conventional PE separator failed at the same C-rate. Using additional electrolyte as plasticizer with suitable polymer networks can lead to high ionic conductivity along with the elevated transference number.⁹⁰ In 2020, Li and colleagues reported a porous film where poly(vinylidene fluoride-cohexafluoropropylene) (PVDF-HFP) was introduced as polymer network.⁹⁰ Confining 1 M LiPF₆ (EC/DEC) to the PVDF-HFP, 0.66 t_{Li+} along with 10^{-3} S cm⁻¹ ionic conductivity was achieved. The Li/LiFePO₄ configuration with the asymmetric GPE also delivered an impressive electrochemical performance, i.e., Coulombic efficiency of 99.5% at 2 C after 600 cycles.

Very recently, Schaefer and colleagues reported a porous gel polymer electrolyte containing 1 M LiPF₆ (EC/DEC) which displayed 1.9×10^{-3} S cm⁻¹ at room temperature and 0.78 t_{Li+} .¹⁰² The unique porous structure was consisted of PEGDMA backbone, without any tethered anions. It was hypothesized that enhanced t_{Li+} was due to reduction of the pore diameter in the presence of electrolyte to length scales comparable to the Debye length. In the Li/LiFePO₄ configuration, the cell with GPE was able to deliver 63.1 mAh g⁻¹ capacity at 5 C whereas, the conventional battery configuration only achieved 51.1 mAh g⁻¹ capacity.

In 2019, Du and coworkers described a cellulose based gel polymer electrolyte containing 1 M LiTFSI in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) with high transport properties, exhibiting a room temperature conductivity of 6.34×10^{-3} S cm⁻¹ with a lithium transference number of 0.82.¹⁰³ While DMSO is not commonly used as a LiB solvent due to chemical instability, the full cell cycling was performed with Li/GPE/LiNi_{0.5}Co_{0.2}Mn_{0.3}O₂ configuration and resulted in 122 mAh g⁻¹ discharge capacity at 0.2 C after 50 cycles with 90% capacity retention.

Figure 6. (a) the dry state of PEGDMA-VS membranes. (b) the SEM image of porous structure of GPE. (c) the performance comparison of GPE (PV2) with 1 M LiTFSI (DOL/DME) electrolyte in Li/S cell to the other compositions of PEGDMA-VS, Celgard and pure PEGDMA homopolymer. (d) The coulombic efficiency with PV2, Celgard and homopolymer PEGDMA. Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Ref. 99 Copyright (2016) American Chemical Society.

In 2020, a comparative study between SIPEs and GPE based on a highly porous lithium sulfonated polyether ether ketone electrospun nanofiber membrane es-LiSPCE was introduced by He and coworkers.¹⁰⁴ Besides the comparison, the porous structure of the polymer is of the striking point of the study. t_{Li^+} of es-LiSPCE-ns (only soaked in EC/DMC solvent, as SIPE) was reported as 0.89. es-LiSPCE-s gelled with 1 M LiPF₆ (EC/DMC) showed slightly lower performance at t_{Li^+} of 0.52 due to the high mobility of the PF₆⁻ anion. Room temperature measured conductivities for es-LiSPCE-ns and es-LiSPCE-s were 1.45×10^{-4} S cm⁻¹ and 2.53×10^{-3} S cm⁻¹ respectively. An outstanding cycling performance was achieved with es-LiSPCE-s at 6 C for over 600 cycles with 130.6 mAh g⁻¹ capacity in the Li/LiFePO₄ configuration.

Recently, Kou and colleagues reported a high performance gel polymer electrolyte prepared by modifying the broadly used polymer PVDF-HFP with porous carbon nanopowder.¹⁰⁵ Different weight ratios of porous carbon powder were doped in the PVDF-HFP matrix at 3% by weight, which resulted in a 3.92×10^{-3} S cm⁻¹ ionic conductivity in the presence of 1 M LiPF₆ (EC/DMC/EMC 1:1:1) liquid electrolyte. Even though, transference number was not reported, the full cycling Li/GPE/LiCoO₂ was resulted with more than 90% coulombic efficiency at 0.1 C. PVDF-HFP has been an attractive material for GPE applications in terms of proving enhanced ionic conductivity along with the transference number.^{90,106–109}

Zhao and coworkers studied a polymer blend with PEG and cellulose as gel polymer electrolytes.¹¹⁰ Ionic conductivity was measured 3.31×10^{-3} S cm⁻¹ and with 5% PEG in the polymer, transference number was 0.63. This study shows that sustainable and different polymers can be modified with traditional and already

proven polymer backbones to create better electrolytes in terms of transport properties for LiBs.

Additionally, in 2020, Kim and colleagues recently published a study on amine-functionalized boron nitride nanosheets as gel electrolyte for lithium ion battery systems with different cathodes.¹¹¹ The ion gel electrolyte was prepared with in-situ thermal polymerization of trimethylolpropane triacrylate (TMPTA) in the presence of PVDF-HFP. At room temperature, ionic conductivity measured 6.47×10^{-4} S cm⁻¹ and $t_{Li^+} = 0.23$ with 1 M LiTFSI (DOL/DME). In comparison to the similar examples, the transport properties are low, but it encourages using different materials to push forward the GPEs for Li-ion battery research area. Another significant point of this study is that some part of it was supported with finite element simulations.

Application of ion Transport Modifying Coatings to Li Metal Anodes

The lithium metal anode is attractive due to its extremely high theoretical capacity (3860 mAh g⁻¹).¹¹² The practical application of Li metal has been limited by both low Coulombic efficiency and Li dendrite formation upon cycling. There are excellent studies and reviews on lithium dendrite formation which are suggested for reader's interests.^{113–116} In recent years, there is a considerable effort to overcome these challenges by modifying the organic electrolyte,^{117,118} improving the interface¹¹⁹ and building 3D host materials for Li metal.¹²⁰ In consideration of all these models, polymer electrolytes are suggested to reduce the formation of lithium dendrites on the lithium metal surface.^{121,122}

There are several proposed models to evaluate dendrite nucleation and growth phenomena. Monroe and Newman predicted

Figure 7. The performance of two of the different GPEs with high transport properties for LiBs by each Li and coworkers and Wang and colleagues. (a) the SEM image of nanoporous sublayer. (b) the C-rate test. (c) the cycling performance of asymmetric GPE in 1 M LiPF_6 (EC/DEC) compared with Celgard in Li/LiFePO_4 . Reproduced (adapted) with permission from Ref. 90 with permission from The Royal Society of Chemistry. (d) the rate capability test for polyethylene (PE) in 1 M LiPF_6 (EC/EMC/DEC) (e), from the rate capability test, GPE in 1 M LiPF_6 (EC/EMC/DEC). Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Ref. 100 Copyright (2019) American Chemical Society.

stabilization of the lithium-electrolyte interface with use of high modulus electrolytes.¹²³ More recently, Viswanthan, Helms, and colleagues predicted and experimentally demonstrated that the optimum chemomechanical design of a solid ion conductor to suppress the dendrite formation should be based on either

pressure-driven (low shear modulus G_s) or density-driven (low Li^+ molar partial volume V_{Li^+}) dendrite suppression.¹²⁴

Aside from mechanical effects of the electrolyte on lithium metal interface stability, ion transport is also proposed to play a key role. Chazalviel suggested that the timescale for dendrite nucleation is

Figure 8. (a) the bare lithium metal surface. (b) PIM-1 (polymer of intrinsic microporosity) coated lithium metal. (c) Li–Cu cells undergoing full plate–strip tests at current density of 0.8 mA cm^{-2} . (e) The capacity fade and Coulombic efficiency for high areal capacity Li–S cells cycled at 0.2 C, where the Li anode incorporates the dendrite-suppressing high cation transference number PIM-1 overlayer. (f) Galvanostatic charge–discharge curves of a high areal capacity Li–S cell at different cycles. Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Ref. 131 Copyright (2019) American Chemical Society.

based on the timescale for anion depletion on the electrode surface, also known as Sand's time (τ_S).¹²⁵ The growth of the dendrites is due to the velocity of anions which depends on the mobility (μ) and the electric field, ($v_i = -\mu_i E$). In 1992, the theory was modified by taking into consideration the electroconvection during electrodeposition and it was shown experimentally that the growth of the lithium dendrites was linked to the current densities.¹²⁶ In 2001, Rosso, Brissot, and colleagues demonstrated that, surprisingly, dendrite nucleation in Li polymer cells occurred at Sand's time with the relationship ($\tau_S = j^{-2}$), despite operation below the limiting current where bulk anion depletion across the electrode-electrolyte interface is not expected.¹²⁷ More recently in 2016, Archer's group expanded upon Chazalviel's theory by taking into consideration the effect of partially fixed anions in a solid electrolyte.¹²⁸

According to the aforementioned theoretical studies, ion concentration gradient and specifically anion depletion at the Li metal surface is one of the reasons for lithium dendrite nucleation. Therefore, restricting the anion motion and increasing the cation transference at the lithium-electrolyte interphase could be a possible solution to prevent the dendrite nucleation. In 2016, Tikekar and coworkers' study covered the basic principles of designing electrolytes and interfaces for stable lithium metal batteries.¹²⁹ Lithium dendrite growing on the lithium metal surface was explained in detail and possible approaches were suggested: improving transport properties, cation transference number, high ionic conductivity, and improving the mechanics of the electrolytes.

Another method is to coat polymer on the lithium metal surface to suppress the dendrite formation as well as enhancing high transport properties locally at this interface, rather than in the bulk electrolyte. This approach is limited to several studies.

Archer's group reported nanometer thick artificially formed SEI by using lithiated ionomers on a lithium metal surface.¹³⁰ Depending on the thickness of the layer, relatively high ionic conductivity ($>5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$) and 0.9 Li^+ transference number were obtained. Visualization of the electrodeposition on the coated lithium showed that lithium dendrite suppression was observed as compared to pristine lithium. In 2019, Helms and colleagues reported a microporous polymer film coated on lithium metal with remarkable outcomes in terms of high transport properties and performance in Li/S cells, as shown in Figure 8.¹³¹ Despite the presence of free anions (-TFSI^-) in the bulk liquid electrolyte, the lithium transference number obtained was 0.72. It was claimed that at the polymer-electrolyte interface, counter ions from the electrolyte may be rejected due to their larger sizes. Hence, Li^+ is the only one that can diffuse in the pore network. Even though controlling lithium dendrite formation is out of the scope of this paper, in terms of lithium surface coating, the study depicts very promising results.

Very recently, Helms' group reported an excellent study on the ion transport mechanism in microporous membranes.¹³² A family of polymers of intrinsic microporosity (PIMs) were synthesized, and some resulted in high ionic conductivity and transference number when exposed to 1 M LiPF_6 in organic carbonate electrolyte. The most optimal material throughout the study; PIM 13 showed 0.205 mS cm^{-1} ionic conductivity and 0.69 transference number at 25°C which led to very promising outcomes for high-voltage lithium metal batteries.

Transport Challenges in Porous Electrodes

Porous electrode design parameters like electrode thickness, porosity, and chemical composition are crucial since they affect

Figure 9. Pathway to higher cell specific energy density. The baseline cell (1) is Li/NMC622 in a pouch cell format, using common values of potential cut-off, excess Li ratio, electrolyte loading, and cathode porosity, mass loading, and thickness. Steps (2), (3), (4), and (6) involve reduction of inactive materials (electrolyte, current collector, casing, etc) relative to active electrode materials. Reprinted (adapted) from Ref. 133 with permission from Nature Publishing Group, copyright 2019.

Figure 10. Schematic of a commercial Panasonic NCR18650-type cylindrical cell consisting of 131 μm thick porous graphite anode and 100 μm thick porous lithium nickel cobalt aluminum oxide (NCA) cathode. 100 μm thickness is widely considered as an active layer thickness not severely sacrificing the rate/capacity performance of the battery. Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Ref. 138.

the energy density and rate capability of the cell. For a specific set of active materials, system energy density is improved by reduction of inactive components (e.g., current collector, casing, electrolyte, etc.)

if active material utilization is maintained. Therefore, increasing areal loading of active materials while maintaining rate capability and without offsetting gains by increases in porosity/electrolyte mass is a necessary component of the strategy to achieve high system energy density as recognized by many authors and shown in Fig. 9. Cell specific energy density of 500 Wh kg⁻¹ is considered critical to reach the former U.S. Department of Energy price target of US\$100/kWh; this target has recently been updated to US\$60/kWh.^{133–135}

As illustrated in Fig. 10, the electrode thicknesses far exceed the electrolyte/separation region thickness in commercial LiBs. Increased thickness and decreased porosity lead to ion and/or electron transport deficiencies, and therefore decreased active material utilization. These challenges have been investigated by both computational and experimental means. Recently, Yang and coworkers addressed the design parameters of thick electrodes for various lithium battery configurations.¹³⁶ It is noted that ion transport, rather than electron transport, is limiting in most cases;¹³⁷ the following discussion will focus on ion transport.

Effective transport properties and porous carbon-binder domain.—The effective conductivity and diffusivity of ions through the porous electrode have paramount importance as they deviate by orders of magnitude from the intrinsic bulk electrolyte properties, due to the tortuous path in the porous electrode. To avoid the modeling of the complex network of interconnected pores in 3D, the complex mass transport can be described by a single effective parameter τ . The following two equations are used to define τ ,

$$\kappa_{\text{eff}} = \kappa \times \frac{\varepsilon}{\tau} \quad [9]$$

$$D_{\text{eff}} = D \times \frac{\varepsilon}{\tau} \quad [10]$$

where κ_{eff} (effective molar conductivity), D_{eff} (effective diffusion coefficient), and κ , D are transport properties and intrinsic transport properties, respectively. Any transport properties are corrected by τ and ε which are the tortuosity and volume fraction of the conductive phase, respectively. For a straight path, $\tau = 1$, or for an increasing tortuosity pathway, $\tau > 1$. Since τ depends on the electrode morphology, τ can be written as a function of ε following the Bruggeman relationship.

$$\kappa_{\text{eff}} = \kappa \varepsilon^{\alpha} \quad [11]$$

Or equivalently, $\tau = \varepsilon^{1-\alpha}$, where ε is the Bruggeman constant. Thorat and colleagues empirically measured the Bruggeman constant as $\alpha = 1.5$ for a continuous conductive phase and $\alpha = 1.53$ for a LiFePO₄ porous electrode.¹⁴⁰

Using the dimensionless MacMullin number N_M , the effect of porous microstructure can be connected to macroscopic conservation laws: $N_M = \kappa/\kappa_{\text{eff}}$ or, $\kappa_{\text{eff}} = \kappa/N_M$. The MacMullin number is connected to the porosity (ε) by a power relationship: $N_M = \varepsilon^{-m}$, where “m” depends on the microstructure of material.^{141,142} MacMullin numbers are different for distinct materials. The graphite electrode of 29% to 35% porosity has a MacMullin number of 18–19, lithium manganese cobalt oxide (NMC) cathodes of similar porosity have 10–11, while commercial electrodes of 30%–35% porosity have MacMullin numbers of 7–20 and lab fabricated electrodes without calendaring have a value of 3–7.^{140,143–147}

The tortuosity values reported in different studies should be scrutinized with great care prior to use, since there are varying definitions of tortuosity and use of the incorrect value could mean a disparate description of the porous microstructure. The size and shape of active particles also influence the tortuosity; lithium cobalt oxide (LiCoO₂) of average particle size of 5 to 20 μm results in a tortuosity of 6.1 to 11. Porosity also has an impact on tortuosity: 25% to 35% porous LiCoO₂ cathode could have tortuosity of 3 to 6.

Diffusivity is also temperature dependent, thus the measured intrinsic diffusivity should be adjusted according to the operating temperature.¹⁴⁸

In 2013, Hutzenlaub and colleagues showed that the carbon-binder-domain (CBD) in between the active particles within the porous electrode should itself be modeled as a porous domain.¹⁴⁸ The porosity and tortuosity of the porous electrode were influenced by the carbon type and amount. The presence of non-active porous carbon-binder-domain created a network of nanopores. The network of nanopores contributed to the theoretical or statistical calculation by increasing the total measured porosity and by reducing the calculated tortuosity, making the tortuosity more homogenous, as mixed nanosized carbon particles with binder contains nanosized pores. In 2018, Usseglio-Viretta's group showed both experimentally and numerically that Bruggeman's relationship cannot be used to account for the CBD morphology. The calculated tortuosity was 1.3 to 1.8 times higher compared to that of the active material skeleton.¹⁴⁹

Vijayaraghavan and coworkers reported that the total macroscopic porosity of the porous cathode was higher than the separately displayed value of packed graphite or active particles.¹⁵⁰ Anisotropic orientation of electrode particles increased the tortuosity and caused a drop of cell capacity, while properly aligned and tightly packed particles ensured higher utilization of active material and increase of capacity.^{149,151} Stephenson and colleagues demonstrated the formation of nanochannels in the CBD which reduced the effective ionic conductivity by 3%–5% from that of the bulk electrolyte.¹⁵²

Hutzenlaub's group reconstructed the three phases—active material, binder, and pore space—to model the battery using Newman's theory.⁹ Acknowledgement of the porous CBD in the interstitial space between active materials is found to be essential for accurate mathematical modeling and optimization of the porous structure of the cathode in order to enhance the effective ionic conductivity.

Limiting factors predicted by mathematical modeling.—

Designing advanced porous cathodes, which are able to perform well during high charge-discharge rates and longer cycling periods, is important for high performance LiBs. To achieve the desired targets, combining theoretical and experimental studies is crucial for the development of porous electrodes. Numerical modeling for investigating electrochemical properties of porous, thick electrodes of Li-ion batteries during charge-discharge is based on porous electrode theory. The following governing equations for porous electrode theory are based on work by Dees and coworkers^{153–155} and Newman and colleagues,^{14,15,156} which are used to determine the salt concentration (c) and electric potential (ϕ) of the electrolyte, where ϵ is porosity, τ is tortuosity, t_+ is transference number (with respect to the solvent), κ is ionic conductivity, i_2 is current carried by charges, and $\left(1 + \frac{\partial \ln f_{\pm}}{\partial \ln c}\right)$ is the thermodynamic factor:

$$\epsilon \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = \frac{\epsilon}{\tau} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(D \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{(1 - t_+) i_2}{F} \right) \quad [12]$$

$$i_2 = -\kappa \frac{\partial \phi_2}{\partial x} - \frac{2RT}{F} \kappa (1 - t_+) \left(1 + \frac{\partial \ln f_{\pm}}{\partial \ln c} \right) \frac{1}{C} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \quad [13]$$

In 2012, Wang and colleagues used a macroscale model of a composite electrode to demonstrate a peak of the local current density curve, which moved from the current collector to the separator, during galvanostatic discharge of a battery.¹³⁹ Results are shown in Figure 11. High local current density caused faster electrochemical reaction and rapid saturation of concentration in the solid phase (no room in the metal oxide lattice for Li⁺ insertion). When the discharge voltage reached the cut-off voltage, a portion of the active material remain unutilized. Therefore, it was determined that optimum electrode thickness and current density are very important for best utilization of active material.¹³⁹

Figure 11. (a) The visualization of the peak current from current collector to separator during intercalation with the optimum cathode thickness 80 μm . (b) The surface concentration at saturation level. Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Ref. 139.

In 2019, Nie and colleagues utilized an in situ neutron imaging method to better understand the governing electrochemical processes during lithiation and delithiation process across the electrodes and to compare with the simulation outcomes.¹⁵⁷ In lithium titanium oxide (LTO) electrode, the peak in Li⁺ ion distribution propagated from the separator side to the current collector side, which was similar phenomena to the observation of the prior mentioned modeling by Wang's group. The thick electrode was affected due to the varying lithiation process across the electrode.¹⁵⁷

By carrying out macroscale simulations, Jiang and Peng identified five important characteristic parameters that impact the capacity: Li⁺ transport rate in the electrolyte phase (t_e), local Li⁺ reduction rate in the electrolyte phase due to redox reactions at the interface (t_c), lithium diffusion rate in the solid phase (t_s), ionic transport resistance (R_e), and electronic transport resistance (R_s).¹⁵⁸ They demonstrated that if the three time parameters were in the same order of magnitude, the limiting factor was not associated with the transport process. For thick electrodes, the slow Li⁺ transport or rapid local depletion of Li⁺ at high rates became the performance limiting factor, while slow lithium diffusion in the solid phase may be a limiting factor for large active particles. Increasing the relative magnitude of R_s to R_e can cause the redox reaction to occur near the current collector, prompting uniform redox reactions throughout the porous electrode.

In Gallagher and colleagues' study, simulated results showed that increasing the current density for a fixed thickness causes a sudden drop in capacity after a certain threshold current density.¹⁵⁹ The knee-point of the capacity profiles displayed a ceiling point of the maximum discharge rate which was able to deliver an attainable capacity close to the nominal value. With increasing thickness, the knee-point shifted to a lower value of optimized current density. Three factors can be assigned to the capacity drop during high charge-discharge rate, as a result of three transport processes: (i) Li^+ diffusion across the electrolyte to the reaction surface of active particles, (ii) Li^+ transport through the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer, and (iii) Li^+ transport through the solid phase of the active materials. In addition, electronic resistance through conductive particles and charge transfer resistance of the electrochemical reaction at the surface of active particles contribute to the total internal resistance.¹⁶⁰

In 2019, Heubner and coworkers computationally examined the capacity drop with increasing C-rate both experimentally and theoretically, which was observed at lower threshold rates in the case of thick electrodes and low porosity, dense electrodes.¹⁶¹ The increased internal resistance due to increased thickness and reduced porosity was observed by impedance spectroscopy. They stated that the diffusion limited current density, (j_{lim}), could be a good indicator of the limiting factor for the electrolyte in the porous cathode, where D_{eff} was defined as the effective diffusivity of electrolyte in porous electrode:

$$j_{\text{lim}} = \frac{2zF D_{\text{eff}} C^0}{L} \quad [13a]$$

Diffusion limited C-rate (DLC) was obtained by dividing the above equation with areal capacity, Q_{areal} .

$$\text{DLC} = \frac{j_{\text{lim}}}{Q_{\text{areal}}} \quad [14]$$

Surpassing the diffusion limited current causes a large over-voltage and side reactions, which induces the reduction of capacity. The achievable capacity is close to the average capacity value, when the applied current rate is lower than the diffusion limiting current. When the current rate crosses the limiting current, the active material utilization and achieved capacity drops dramatically.¹⁶¹

Limiting factors of thick electrode observed by experimental evidence.—Equivalent circuit of the general transmission line model is used to interpret the Nyquist plot data from impedance spectroscopy in order to determine the internal resistance and ionic conductivity of porous cathodes and porous separators.^{140,147,162,163} In 2015, Ogihara and coworkers reported that the internal resistance of a porous electrode was composed of concentration polarization, potential polarization, and ohmic resistance of the network of conductive carbon.¹³⁷ The study suggested that when electrode thickness is increased, ion transport resistance is also increased by making Li^+ ion conduction in the porous domain a rate determining factor, whereas charge transfer resistance of the faradic reaction at the active material surface plays a minor role. Charge transfer resistance becomes a rate determining factor for thin electrodes and ionic resistance has minimal effect in that case.

Du and coworkers addressed the problems associated with the thick electrodes: polarization of cells and rapid saturation of active material surface, which brought on under-utilization of the active materials.¹⁶⁴ These results were also in good agreement with Wang's group's simulation results.¹³⁹ The effective Li^+ ion diffusion through the porous domain, a limitation for high-rate performance, becomes an important intrinsic property of thick and dense electrodes.¹⁶⁴ Newman's, Zheng's, and Mei's groups used the Ragone plot as a significant indicator for the performance of batteries with thick electrodes by comparing the energy density plotted against power density.^{165–167} In Zheng's and coworkers'

Figure 12. (a) The inverse relationship between energy and power of the LIB by using NCM and LFP cathodes with different thickness. (b) The effect of thickness on energy and power density. Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Ref. 166.

study, the Ragone plot showed that increased energy density is accompanied by a drop of power density, and while a thicker electrode causes an increase of energy density because of the proportional reduction of non-active material it also induces a rapid drop of power density, which is displayed in Fig. 12.¹⁶⁶ This deteriorating power relationship with increased thickness is a proof of underutilization of active material.

Newman's, Zheng's, and Mei's groups along with other research groups showed that the high polarization and internal resistance across the porous cathode with increasing thickness and declining porosity result in capacity loss and higher rate of ohmic heat generation and poor cyclic performance.^{159,166,167,173,174} Capacity fading is a common phenomenon in case of thick electrodes greater than 100 μm for average porosity of 30%–35%.^{159,166,175,176}

In 2019, Mei and colleagues reported on the increased heat generation and degraded power density in the cell due to increased thickness of electrode investigated with an electrochemical-thermal coupling model.¹⁶⁷ The study explained that generated heat during charging-discharging of the battery can be categorized into two types: reversible heat that was generated by the reversible process of insertion-extraction in active material and irreversible heat caused by irreversible processes such as overpotential induced polarization heat and internal resistance induced ohmic heat. Increased electrode thickness caused a surge of ohmic heat due to the increase of potential gradient and concentration gradient.¹⁶⁵ The increasing overpotential that quantifies the deviation of electrode potential

Table I. Summary of high capacity/thick electrodes for high performance LiBs between 2011 and 2021. “-” indicates that the current density or areal capacity cannot be calculated with the available published information.

Electrode material	Electrode thickness	Electrolyte type	Current density	C-rate	Areal capacity	Capacity utilization	Theoretical capacity	Electrode processing/ fabrication method	Year	References
LiFePO ₄	40 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DEC 1:1 v%)	—	1 C	3.25 mAh cm ⁻²	76%	4.3 mAh cm ⁻²	Conventional methods (ionomer binder)	2011	172
LiNi _{1/3} Mn _{1/3} Co _{1/3} O ₂	1200 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DMC 1:1 v%)	—	0.1 C	8.4 mAh cm ⁻²	142%	5.9 mAh cm ⁻²	Metal foam (porous) current collector	2011	178
LiNi _{0.8} Co _{0.15} Al _{0.05} O ₂	100 μm	1.2 M LiPF ₆ (EC-EMC 3:7 wt%)	—	0.2 C	1.52 mAh cm ⁻²	66%	2.3 mAh cm ⁻²	Conventional methods	2011	179
LiFePO ₄	108 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DEC 1:1 wt%)	—	1 C	3.4 mAh cm ⁻²	126%	2.7 mAh cm ⁻²	Conventional methods	2012	166
LiNi _{1/3} Mn _{1/3} Co _{1/3} O ₂	104 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DEC 1:1 wt%)	—	1 C	2.3 mAh cm ⁻²	35%	6.5 mAh cm ⁻²	Conventional methods	2012	166
LiCoO ₂	220 μm	1.3 M LiPF ₆ (in alkyl carbonate)	~ 13.4 mA cm ⁻²	2 C	6.7 mAh cm ⁻²	41%	16.3 mAh cm ⁻²	Co-extrusion method	2013	180
LiNi _{1/3} Mn _{1/3} Co _{1/3} O ₂	70 μm	LP ₃₀ with Vinylene carbonate (11.5 wt% LiPF ₆ / 42.8 wt% EC/42.8 wt % DMC/2.9 wt%)	—	0.2 C	5.24 mAh cm ⁻²	114%	4.6 mAh cm ⁻²	Conventional methods	2015	175
LiNi _{1/3} Mn _{1/3} Co _{1/3} O ₂	320 μm	LP ₃₀ with Vinylene carbonate (11.5 wt% LiPF ₆ / 42.8 wt% EC/42.8 wt % DMC/2.9 wt%)	—	0.2 C	5.48 mAh cm ⁻²	202%	2.71 mAh cm ⁻²	Conventional methods	2015	175
LiNi _{0.6} Mn _{0.2} Co _{0.2} O ₂	154 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (3:7 wt% EC/EMC with 2 wt% vinylene Carbonate)	1 mA cm ⁻²	—	5.8 mAh cm ⁻²	90%	6.4 mAh cm ⁻²	Conventional methods	2015	159
LiFePO ₄ with multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWNTs) as a conductive additive	1400 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DEC 1:1 v%)	~ 1.25 mA cm ⁻²	0.2 C	10.5 mAh cm ⁻²	105%	10 mAh cm ⁻²	Binder replacement	2015	181
LiNi _{1/3} Mn _{1/3} Co _{1/3} O ₂	305 μm	LP ₃₀ with vinylene carbonate (LiPF ₆ , 42.8 wt.%/ EC, 42.8 wt.%/ DMC, 2.9 wt.%)	~ 1.09 mA cm ⁻²	0.1 C	9.2 mAh cm ⁻²	220%	4.2 mAh cm ⁻²	Conventional methods	2016	182
LiFePO ₄ with CF (Carbon framework)	800 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DMC 1:1 v%)	0.5 mA cm ⁻²	—	7.6 mAh cm ⁻²	74%	10.2 mAh cm ⁻²	3D current collectors	2017	183
LiFePO ₄ (8 layers)	1500 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DMC/DEC 1:1:1 v %)	~ 1.34 mA cm ⁻²	0.1 C	7.5 mAh cm ⁻²	88%	8.5 mAh cm ⁻²	3D printing	2018	184
LiFePO ₄ with conductive nanofiber	320 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DEC 50-50 v%)	2 mA cm ⁻²	—	8.8 mAh cm ⁻²	86%	10.2 mAh cm ⁻²	Conductive 3D binder network	2018	185
LiCoO ₂	600 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/EMC 1:1 wt%)	0.38 mA cm ⁻²	—	16.7 mAh cm ⁻²	50%	33.4 mAh cm ⁻²	Porous Current collector	2018	186

Table I. (Continued).

Electrode material	Electrode thickness	Electrolyte type	Current density	C-rate	Areal capacity	Capacity utilization	Theoretical capacity	Electrode processing/fabrication method	Year	References
LiFePO ₄	1000 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DMC 1:1 wt.%)	—	0.2 C	20 mAh cm ⁻²	—	—	Plasma Sintering method	2018	187
Li ₄ Ti ₅ O ₁₂	1000 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DMC 1:1 wt.%)	—	0.2 C	20 mAh cm ⁻²	—	—	Plasma Sintering method	2018	187
LiFePO ₄	170 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DEC 50-50 v%)	0.2 mA cm ⁻²	—	2.5 mAh cm ⁻²	89%	2.8 mAh cm ⁻²	Aerosol jet printing	2019	188
LiNi _{0.5} Mn _{0.3} Co _{0.2} O ₂	175 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DEC 1:1 v%)	—	2 C	10 mAh cm ⁻²	—	—	Laser structured	2019	168
LiCoO ₂	400 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DEC 1:1 v%)	—	0.1 C	10.2 mAh cm ⁻²	37%	37 mAh cm ⁻²	Cold sintering process	2019	170
LiFePO ₄	500 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DMC 1:1wt%)	—	C/24 C	13.3 mAh cm ⁻²	78%	17.1 mAh cm ⁻²	Powdered extrusion moulding	2019	189
Li ₄ Ti ₅ O ₁₂	550 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DMC 1:1wt%)	—	C/24 C	13.3 mAh cm ⁻²	76%	17.1 mAh cm ⁻²	Powdered extrusion moulding	2019	189
LiNi _{1/3} Mn _{1/3} Co _{1/3} O ₂	220 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/EMC 3:7 wt.% with 2wt.% vinylene carbonate)	3 mA cm ⁻²	—	7.1 mAh cm ⁻²	53%	13.3 mAh cm ⁻²	Improving drying process	2020	190
Li ₄ Ti ₅ O ₁₂ with reduced graphene oxide and silver nanowire conductive additives (rGO-AgNWs)	1050 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DEC/DMC 1:1:1 v%)	1.06 mA cm ⁻²	—	4.74 mAh cm ⁻²	90%	5.2 mAh cm ⁻²	3D printing	2020	169
LiFePO ₄	1300 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DMC 1:1 v%)	—	10 C	15.1 mAh cm ⁻²	67%	22.5 mAh cm ⁻²	Phase inversion method	2021	191
LiCoO ₂	700 μm	1 M LiPF ₆ (EC/DMC 1:2 v%)	—	0.1 C	25 mAh cm ⁻²	81%	30 mAh cm ⁻²	Laser structured	2021	192

from the equilibrium potential induces the increase of polarization heat because of the increased electrode thickness, maintaining a proportional relationship.^{166,167,173,174,177}

The profound impact of electrode thickness on energy density and rate capability of lithium batteries has been investigated by many research groups. The most recent and notable works are summarized in Table I and discussed in the following sections on electrode structuring and binder chemistry strategies attempted to improve performance of higher loading electrodes.

In-situ/operando characterization of electrode materials.—We note that several detailed reviews on in-situ or *operando* characterization techniques, that are used to investigate electrode lithiation, degradation, redox mechanisms, interfacial chemistry, thermal decomposition, ion distribution, and ion transport properties, were published.^{193–198} With respect to ion transport phenomena impacting capacity utilization, in-situ and *operando* investigations are particularly useful for determining the spatial distribution of lithiation extent within electrodes. As previously mentioned, in-situ neutron imaging has been applied.¹⁵⁷ Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) also has the advantage of being non-destructive; it does not require a large electric field for signal evolution, thus avoiding electrolyte degradation.^{199,200} X-ray tomography is an in-situ characterization to analyze the electrode components, different phases within the porous electrode, and create 3D reconstructions of complex porous structures for mathematical modeling. It is also used to analyze lithium intercalation and material rupture during cycling.^{201–203}

Improvement of Thick Electrodes

Manufacturing methods and anisotropic materials may be leveraged to yield more direct transport pathways and alleviate the transport limitations that arise when employing thicker, porous electrode layers.²⁰⁴ These approaches that specifically target the improvement of ion transport via structuring of porous electrodes are described below, along with brief mention of works where electronic transport was emphasized.

Conventional methods.—Before introducing advanced methods for fabrication of thick electrodes, we highlight studies in which thick electrodes (in the range of 100–300 μm) are fabricated by conventional cathode casting and calendaring techniques. Hahn and coworkers presented LiNiCoMnO_2 (NMC) cathodes with various thickness.^{175,182} It was reported that the cell with NMC 305 μm thick displayed 436 Wh L^{-1} energy density at 0.1 C. In 2011, Henrikson and colleagues reported that $\text{LiNi}_x\text{Co}_y\text{Al}_z\text{O}_2$ (NCA) cathode with 100 μm was found to be the most promising cathode for plug-in hybrid vehicle applications.¹⁷⁹

The electronically conductive network throughout the thick electrode is a major factor affecting the utilization of the active material. In 2019, Park and coworkers prepared thick cathodes, up to 800 μm , including carbon nanotubes with various lithium storage materials (graphite, metal oxide).²⁰⁵ The composite electrode showed in order of 10^{-4} S cm^{-1} conductivity which resulted in low charge transfer resistance and fast charge delivery. The cathode exhibited ~ 29 mAh cm^{-2} discharge capacity in contrast to commercial electrode (~ 4 mAh cm^{-2}) despite the very high mass loading of both cathodes (167 mg cm^{-2}). Graphene based materials are also suggested as effective conductive additives to achieve high electronic conductivity because of their high tensile strength and high electrical conductivity of up to 10^4 S m^{-1} .^{206–208}

In 2018, Kuang and colleagues reported, a scalable and cost-effective method of making a conductive 3D network by mixing cellulose nanofiber with carbon-black nanoparticles for LiFePO_4 (LFP) cathodes with high mass loading.¹⁸⁵ The battery which was consisted of Li metal and LFP with 60 mg cm^{-2} mass loading was able to deliver 8.8 mAh cm^{-2} capacity at 0.5 mA cm^{-2} . In 2021, Yoo and colleagues introduced a multifunctional poly(melamine-formaldehyde) (MF) additive to improve the electrochemical properties of an LiCoO_2 (LCO) cathode.²⁰⁹ The addition of MF-copolymer

to the cathode slurry with PVDF led to contact enhancement between active particles and carbon nanotubes. The cathode with 16.5 mAh cm^{-2} displayed 139 mAh g^{-1} discharge capacity at 5 C.

In 2020, Wohlfahrt-Mehrens and colleagues investigated the porous structure of the carbon-binder-domain produced by the low shear mixing technique.¹⁹⁰ This technique was found desirable for cathode fabrication due to the improvement of the carbon-binder-domain distribution and cathode morphology, which increases the effective conductivity. High shear mixing was not preferable since it caused disintegration of long PVDF chains. Furthermore, the lower viscosity induced inhomogeneous distribution of particles during drying which reduced the nominal capacity of the cathode to only 15% at high current rate (1 C).

Fonts and coworkers reported that the slow solvent drying process at lower temperature, in lieu of the industrial method of high temperature conductive fast drying, produces thick electrodes that demonstrate capacity improvement by 60% at high current rate.²¹⁰ Their findings ensured that inhomogeneous distribution of binder due to high shear mixture and fast drying causes deterioration of capacity.

Zhu and colleagues used rapid evaporation techniques to create vertically aligned nanosheets (VANS) based electrodes from 2D VOPO_4 nanosheets that exhibit better electrochemical performance in thick electrodes.²¹¹ VANS based electrodes with 500 g m^{-2} mass loading achieved ~ 80 mA g^{-1} at 10 C- rate, while conventional electrodes with same material loading was not able cycle higher than 5 C. The performance improvement was related to the directional orientation of materials, endowing faster lithium ion flux.²¹¹ This powerful fabrication technique can be extended to other conventional active materials that can be synthesized as nanosheets.

Restructuring of the porous electrode.—The tortuous path within porous electrodes reduces the effective ionic conductivity and power density especially with thick active layers, and commercially deployable methods of restructuring the ion transport pathway are attractive ways to improve the effective ionic conductivity. Engineering the pores inside the electrode can provide more space to allow Li^+ to diffuse more effectively. Electrodes of thicknesses close to or higher than 100 μm and mass loading of greater than 20 mg cm^{-2} can benefit from new manufacturing methods that build upon the conventional electrode casting technique. Different approaches like metal foams and carbon textile based thick cathodes,^{212,213} 3D embroidered aluminum current collectors,²¹⁴ formation of vertical open channels to the current collector^{215,216} and sintered binder-free electrodes,^{217,218} laser structuring to create through holes till current collector^{219–223} and mud cracking,¹⁷⁶ are suggested to orient the ion transport pathways and reduce tortuosity within thick electrodes.

In 2011, Tataria and coworkers introduced Cu and Al foam current collectors for graphite anodes and NMC cathodes with 1200 μm thickness respectively.¹⁷⁸ At 0.1 C the cell delivered 8.4 mAh cm^{-2} capacity. In the following years, the 3D current collectors have been utilized in different cathode materials and thickness. In 2017, Hu and coworkers reported a 800 μm thick LFP cathode with 60 mg cm^{-2} mass loading in which highly conductive, low tortuosity carbon framework was utilized as the 3D current collector.¹⁸³ The cell was able to deliver 7.4 mAh cm^{-2} capacity and energy density of 26 mWh cm^{-2} at 0.5 mA cm^{-2} current density. Qiao's group reported a porous metal current collector for LCO cathode (600 μm) and demonstrated 16.7 mAh cm^{-2} areal capacity (compared to theoretical 19.2 mAh cm^{-2}) at 0.38 mA cm^{-2} current density.¹⁸⁶

In 2018, Seznec and colleagues used salt templating of sodium chloride to create micron size pores in very thick LFP electrodes which were spark plasma sintered to maintain mechanical integrity.¹⁸⁷ The achieved high discharge capacity was 140 mAh g^{-1} . Sanders and colleagues used magnetized nylon rods to create anisotropic ordering across the porous LCO cathodes.²¹⁶ Due to ordered and directional pores, the thick electrode delivered higher areal capacity of 8.1 mAh cm^{-2} , more than twice of the reference electrode of similar thickness and density, at 1.94 C.

Figure 13. Park and colleagues laser cut uniformly spaced micro-grooves on an NMC cathode. (a) and (b) unstructured and structured electrodes with high porosity. (c) and (d) the cross-section of each electrode. (e) and (f) specific energy and discharge capacity at various C-rates. (Low_S_x and Low_U_x represents structured and unstructured electrode of x thickness and low porosity; High_S_x and High_U_x represents same features but of high porosity). Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Ref. 168.

In 2021, Chen and coworkers reported an ultrahigh capacity (15.1 mAh cm⁻²) thick (1300 μm) LFP cathode with vertically aligned micro channels which were prepared by a phase inversion method.¹⁹¹ The unique micro channels prompted the fast ion transport in which the discharge capacity was 110 mAh g⁻¹ at 10 C.

Using lasers to restructure the ion transport path is considered promising as it is a fast and reliable fabrication technique. In 2019, Tsuda and coworkers used pico-second pulsed lasers to create through- and non-through holes of 20–30 μm average diameter grooved on ultra-thick LFP cathodes.²²² Impedance spectroscopy on these electrodes showed lower internal resistances. The cycling results displayed major improvement for through-holed and non-through holed LFP cathodes. The through-holed electrode showed a smaller IR drop and higher capacity of 100 mAh g⁻¹ at 10 C, in comparison to control electrode with 80 mAh g⁻¹ capacity. The formation of holes largely improved high-rate performance of the thick cathodes; increased surface area and reduced tortuosity facilitates this improvement.

Ultrafast or nanosecond (ns)-laser and 3D laser techniques were used by several groups to restructure the porous structure and make grooves to enhance the ion transport properties.^{220–222} In 2020, Pflüger reviewed the recent laser techniques for battery materials for large scale future applications.²²⁴

Park and coworkers used a femtosecond laser to make grooves which displayed nearly double specific energy at high current rates (2 C, 3 C) for structured thick electrode (175 μm) compared to a conventional electrode of same porosity, density, and material loading. Irrespective of electrode thickness, the structured electrode exhibited an increase in peak current and a drop in cell polarization with respect to the normal electrode, as it is displayed in Fig. 13.¹⁶⁸

Recently, Kim and colleagues reported ultra-thick LCO (700 μm) and graphite anode (650 μm) with 25 mAh cm⁻² areal capacity which were prepared by laser structuring.¹⁹² The geometric changes resulted in decrease in the tortuosity and both ionic and electronic resistances which led to increased rate capability. The structured cathode's discharge capacity was 15 mAh cm⁻² at 0.1 C whereas, the unstructured cell was able to deliver approximately 2.5 mAh cm⁻².

In 2018, Lee and coworkers applied the mud-cracking technique for electrode fabrication to form an array of tiny vertical pathways to reduce the tortuosity and resulting ionic resistance.¹⁷⁶ The ionic conductivity through the electrode increased from 0.141 to 0.234 mS cm⁻¹ with the increase of crack density. At high discharge rate, the voltage plateau was higher compared to the voltage plateau of traditional cathodes and the dQ/dV ~ V plot shows a shift of Co³⁺/Co⁴⁺ reduction peaks to higher voltage range and reduced intensity.

3D printing methods.—3D printing methods were used to improve the areal capacity of cathodes based on various active materials.^{169,188,225–227} In 2018, Sun and coworkers reported 1500 μm thick, 50 mg cm⁻² areal loading LFP cathodes with different patterns in which 3D printing technique was utilized.¹⁸⁴ The cell with 8 printed layers resulted in approximately 7.5 mAh cm⁻² capacity and a power density of 2.99 mW cm⁻² at 0.1 C.

In 2020, Sun and colleagues used 3D printing to create a highly conductive matrix of LTO, silver nanowires, and graphene, utilizing the facile extrusion based process of viscous gel like nanocomposites.¹⁶⁹ As it is illustrated in Fig. 14, the gel-like slurry was printed in order, and

Figure 14. The illustration of the fabrication process of a 3D printed architecture, made of silver nanowire (AgNW), graphene oxide (GO), and LTO nanoparticles. Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Ref. 169.

Figure 15. A schematic illustration of the electrode fabricated by cold sintering process (CSP); co-sintering of inorganic material (LCO, Ga-doped $\text{Li}_7\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_{12}$ (LLZGO) nanoparticles and carbon black) and organic polymer (PEO) into a dense pellet at low temperature. a) The structure of the conventional electrode fabricated by slurry coating with tortuous and long ion diffusion path. b) The structure of dense electrode with a large thickness prepared by CSP technology. c) The cycling performance of CSP made electrode and conventional electrode in Li/LiCoO₂ cells at 0.1 C. Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Ref. 170.

after freeze drying and chemical reduction, the 3D printed filaments were stacked closely in uniform layers. The hierarchical network was composed of uniformly distributed channels between layers and sporadic nanoporous pathways. The 3D electrode (150 μm) based batteries exhibited improved rate capability (120 mAh g⁻¹ against 20 mAh g⁻¹ for conventional at 10 C) and specific capacity at high current rate (91% against 31% for conventional, after 200 cycles).

In 2019, Deiner and coworkers utilized wide printhead of the aerosol jets and multiple nozzles of the inkjet to enable faster speed of 3D printing of cathodes.¹⁸⁸ The aerosol jet printed LFP cathode (170 μm) had a hierarchically porous microstructure and patterned surface which cannot be achieved by conventionally casting methods. In between several hundred micrometer long aligned needles, the channels of few micrometer width were surrounded by cathode material made of primary particles. This resulted in three times higher pore volume than conventionally cast cathode (which has 1.7 nm to 300 nm pores) and a density of 0.9–1.0 g cm⁻³,

compared with 1.8 g cm⁻³ for commercially cast LFP electrode. The jet printed 170 μm thick LFP cathodes demonstrated higher capacity and better stability during cycling at high current rate of 1 C retaining 93% of primary capacity.

Powder extrusion and sintering.—Powder extrusion molding is a viable, environmentally friendly, and cost-effective alternative for the fabrication of high energy electrodes. The powder extrusion molding based fabrication method was previously used by Sotomayor and colleagues to manufacture yttria stabilized zirconia and nickel-yttria stabilized zirconia electrolytes and anodes for solid oxide fuel cell applications.^{228,229}

Sotomayor's group used carbon coated LTO and LFP active material powders with the binder dedicated for powder extrusion molding to prepare a pseudoplastic feedstock by utilizing a twin-screw extruder, that is followed by a solvent-thermal debinding process for polymer removal and sintering at high temperature.¹⁸⁹

The additive-free thick ceramic electrodes of LTO and LFP, obtained from this solvent-free technique, achieved a high capacity of 130 mAh g^{-1} and high energy density and moderate capacity loss after 50 cycles at C/12 rate, despite being $\sim 500 \mu\text{m}$ thick and with a mass loading of 1000 g m^{-2} , while commercial electrodes were $\sim 100 \mu\text{m}$ thick and with a mass loading of $200\text{--}225 \text{ g m}^{-2}$.

The cold sintering process was recently leveraged by Wu and coworkers to fabricate ultra-thick cathodes by co-sintering organic binder, inorganic active material, and conductive material at temperatures below 200°C .¹⁷⁰ A schematic of the fabricated electrodes and cycling data are shown in Fig. 15. Because of the continuous ion-interaction pathway in the thick film, the co-sintered pellets were able to achieve high rate capability, areal capacity, and energy density. The $400 \mu\text{m}$ thick cathode achieved high specific capacity of 131.2 mAh g^{-1} and was able to retain 96 % capacity after 150 cycles at 0.1 C, while the commercial cathode of $40 \mu\text{m}$ resulted in 39 % capacity retention. Bae and coworkers threaded an array of periodic channels across the porous sintered electrodes by iterative sintering and co-extrusion through a die, which was beneficial to reduce the salt polarization and to minimize the capacity deterioration for the thick electrodes.¹⁸⁰

Improvement of Thick Electrodes Through Active Binder

Inactive components of the porous cathode such as the binder and conductive carbon are crucial to provide the mechanical strength and maintenance of electrical connectivity to each of the active particles. The disconnection between the particles in the electrode and from the current collector during cycling is avoided through intermolecular forces and polymer entanglement.^{230–236}

The network of tortuous ion transport channels built by the dispersed polymer binder and conductive carbon in the inactive region of cathode conducts the moving ions to the reaction surface of active particles. The conventional fluoropolymer binders for cathodes such as polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) or PVDF do not possess any intrinsic ion transport property and the ion transport is driven by diffusion and migration through the tortuous, liquid-filled ion conducting channels. With regard to a conventional LiB, on type of ion is active in the electrochemical process, and the mobile counter ions are polarized due to the electric field. The loss incurred by this ionic polarization has a severe effect the performance of the cell, especially in thick electrode. When ion conducting polymer is used as a replacement of conventional fluoropolymer binder or as a blend with conventional fluoropolymer binder, the functional tethered ligands may facilitate ion transport to compensate the salt depletion near the active material surface. The severe concentration gradient may be prevented and the polarization reduced. Thus, the battery can perform better at higher charge and discharge rates.^{171,172,237,238}

Wei and colleagues used a lithiated ionomer with PTFE-type backbone and short side chains as a binder in a LFP electrode.¹⁷¹

The polymer binder had a high cation exchange capacity ($\sim 1.1 \text{ meq g}^{-1}$), and the fluorinated chemical structure showed high oxidative stability, rendering overall better cycling performance. Sulfonated polyether ketone (SPEEK) with the lithiated sulfonated side chains (SPEEK-FSA-Li) was effectively used as an ion conductive binder by multiple research groups.^{171,239,240} Anionic polymer chains of ionomers (perfluorosulfonic acid side chain ionomers) could spread into the liquid electrolyte while delocalization of negative charges on the sulfonate backbone facilitates the solvation-desolvation of Li^+ ions. This leads to the formation of effective nanoscale ion conducting channels in which higher Li^+ transport and conductivity are able to be achieved.^{171,172,241} The modified LFP cathode by Wei's group displayed better capacity of $\sim 142 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$, against $\sim 135 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$ (for conventional cathodes) improving by $\sim 5\%$, at 0.5 C and higher discharge plateau of 3.37 V against 3.29 V. At 2 C, the capacity improvement was higher by 8% in contrast to at lower C-rates as it is displayed in Figs. 16a–16b.¹⁷¹

Figure 16. (a) The comparison of charge/discharge profile of used SPEEK-FSA-Li ionomer based and PVDF based cathodes. (b) The C-rate test. Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Ref. 171 (c) The discharge curves of lithiated perfluorosulfonate ionomer with PTFE-like backbone and PVDF based $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}/\text{LiFePO}_4$ cells with 1 M LiPF_6 (EC/DEC). (d) The discharge curves with 0.1 M LiPF_6 (EC/DEC). Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Ref. 172.

Shi and colleagues used a blend of lithiated poly(perfluoroalkylsulfonyl)imide (PFSILi) and PVDF at 1:1 weight ratio as the binder for a LFP cathode.²⁴¹ The cation exchange capacity of PFSILi was ~ 2.9 meqg⁻¹. The Li/LiFePO₄ cell with ionic binder had 379 mWhg⁻¹ specific capacity whereas, the cell with the PVDF binder had slightly lower utilization, 334 mWhg⁻¹. At room temperature, the performance difference was not distinguished. However, at 60°C, the energy density of the cell with the active binder improved due to the decrease polarization resistance. In 2014, Chiu and colleagues used lithiated perfluorosulfonate ionomer binder in an LMO cathode and reported performance improvement at high C-rates (5 C to 20 C) at 60 °C.²³⁸

Pan and coworkers used lithiated bis(benzene sulfonyl)imide to reduce the interfacial resistance significantly while simultaneously providing mechanical strength as adhesive binder.²⁴² Oh and coworkers utilized a lithiated ionomer with perfluorosulfonic acid side chains as active binder with a LFP cathode.¹⁷² The ionomer contributed an additional 60% of Li⁺ to the electrolyte in the pores in addition to the free salt. In the case of 1 M LiPF₆ (EC/DEC), the capacity of ionomer based cathode at 5 C, was 87 mAh g⁻¹ whereas, the cathode with PVDF was 78 mAh g⁻¹, exhibiting $\sim 11.5\%$ improvement of improvement as demonstrated in Figs. 16 c–16d. In 0.1 M LiPF₆ (EC/DEC), the capacity improvement at 5 C was much greater in the case of cathode with ionomer, than that with PVDF, being 75 mAh g⁻¹ and 57 mAh g⁻¹ respectively with an improvement of $\sim 32\%$. Since Li⁺ ion depletion was higher in the case of low salt concentration, the compensation from ionomer was observed for the case of low salt concentration electrolyte. Vadivel and Sawangphruk investigated prelithiated Nafion ionomer dissolved in ethanol and NMP solvent as binder for fabricating NCA cathode, to study alternative conductive binder that can be utilized for Ni-rich cathodes.²⁴³ The ethanol solvent utilized Nafion based cathodes exhibit higher capacity and cyclability.

Additionally, toxic and environmentally hazardous NMP/PVDF can be replaced by water soluble binder.^{244,245} Passerini and coworkers published an extensive review on alternative binders for sustainable energy storage materials.²⁴⁶ The crosslinked water soluble lithiated copolymer (LPPS) was synthesized and used as binder for LFP batteries by Wu and Duh.²⁴⁷ The LPPS binder showed 140 mAh g⁻¹ at 5 C compared to 120 mAh g⁻¹ for the control PVDF based cathode, improving by $\sim 16.7\%$. At 1 C, the capacity retention was 95% capacity after 200 cycles, whereas the capacity retention for the PVDF based cathode was only 63% and at 0.5 C ionomer based cathode was able to achieve 178 mAh g⁻¹ close to theoretical capacity while PVDF based cathode was not able exceed 145 mAh g⁻¹. Other non-active aqueous binder such as non-fluorinated carboxy-methylcellulose (CMC) are also very promising and can be used in polymer blends.²⁴⁸ In some studies, poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene):poly(styrene sulfonic acid) (PEDOT:PSS) with polyethylene oxide (PEO) or sulfonated polyphenylene oxide (SPPO) was used as active cathode binder for thick LFP cathodes.^{249–255} Armand and coworkers introduced polyether amines oligomer side chains (i.e., Jeffamine® compounds) as both self-standing SPE electrolyte and cathode binder.²⁵⁶ The material displayed good conductivity at room temperature and exhibited stability as binder for LFP cathodes.

Polar binders like poly(acrylic acid) (PAA), poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA), and poly(methacrylic acid) (PMA) were used by Komaba and colleagues for the graphite electrode.^{257,258} PAA binder created a layer on the active particles and unshared electron pairs of the carboxyl group (COOH) and electron pair of OH group could interact with solvated lithium ions, accelerating the desolvation and Li⁺ insertion in active materials. Xu and colleagues used ferroelectric (β) PVDF polymer binder over the conventional paraelectric (α) PVDF polymer binder since the polarity of polymer chain helped to increase the Li⁺ ion diffusivity by solvation-desolvation and ensures strong attachment to active materials.²⁵⁹

Gong and Tsao groups used polyacrylic nitrile (PAN) based polymer binder containing nitrile groups to enhance the ionic conductivity in the electrode.^{260,261} The PEO-b-PAN based block copolymer functioned as a promising ion-conducting active binder for LFP based batteries due to increasing the effective surface contact, reducing the interfacial resistance and electrolyte resistance.²⁶¹ Highly polar PAN is an electrochemically efficient and chemically stable binder for commercial graphite, LTO, and Si/C, producing low hydrofluoric acid (HF) content and with strong adhesion strength.^{235,258} Other hydroxyl group-containing binders have a propensity to form more HF byproducts when fluorinated salts are used in the electrolyte, which may lead to undesirable electrode-electrolyte interfacial chemistry.^{258,262,263} Poly(acrylic acid) and poly(ethylene glycol-co-benzimidazole) were used in the silicon (Si) anodes, and it was reported that they are capable of enabling higher specific capacity by accelerating the transport of Li⁺ ions.²⁶⁴

Conclusions

Higher energy density and power density of rechargeable batteries is much desired towards increasing electrification of transportation and reducing the need for combustion of fossil fuels. Ion transport properties within bulk electrolytes and porous electrodes have a substantial influence on battery system performance as evidenced by theory, simulation, and experiment.

Liquid, binary salt containing electrolytes are still the state of the art in lithium-ion batteries due to their relatively high ionic conductivity and low cost, despite their low transference number. Polymer based electrolytes, coatings, and binders can enable enhanced lithium transference and higher rate capability while adding less inactive mass to the system than inorganic electrolytes. Polymer design to enhance cation transport while maintaining mechanical, electrochemical, and chemical stability with target electrode materials should be a primary target of future research efforts.

Next generation fabrication techniques for ultrathick cathodes have been explored, like dry cathode fabrication techniques and 3D printing, which could revolutionize the manufacturing process of commercial batteries to decrease production cost and increase active material utilization and system energy density. Electrode sintering is garnering attention and support in the commercial space due to its solvent-free, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly nature coupled with the resulting controlled, favorable porous morphology.

The challenge still remains to engineer electrolyte and electrode materials and architectures to maximize achievable energy and power density of lithium batteries, regardless of the electrode couple.

ORCID

Alberto Salvadori <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4875-7059>

Jennifer L. Schaefer <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4293-6328>

References

1. J. B. Goodenough and Y. Kim, "Challenges for rechargeable Li batteries." *Chem. Mater.*, **22**, 587 (2010).
2. S. Mogurampelly, O. Borodin, and V. Ganesan, "Computer simulations of ion transport in polymer electrolyte membranes." *Annu. Rev. Chem. Biomol. Eng.*, **7**, 349 (2016).
3. O. Borodin, G. D. Smith, and R. Douglas, "Force field development and MD simulations of poly(ethylene oxide)/LiBF₄ polymer electrolytes." *J. Phys. Chem. B*, **107**, 6824 (2003).
4. D. Diddens, A. Heuer, and O. Borodin, "Understanding the lithium transport within a rouse-based model for a peo/litfsi polymer electrolyte." *Macromolecules*, **43**, 2028 (2010).
5. H. Arunachalam, S. Korneev, I. Battiato, and S. Onori, "Multiscale modeling approach to determine effective lithium-ion transport properties." *American Control Conference*, 92 (2017).
6. A. G. Kashkooli, S. Farhad, D. U. Lee, K. Feng, S. Litster, S. K. Babu, L. Zhu, and Z. Chen, "Multiscale modeling of lithium-ion battery electrodes based on nanoscale X-ray computed tomography." *J. Power Sources*, **307**, 496 (2016).

7. R. Mahbub et al., "Quantitative analysis of multi-scale heterogeneities in complex electrode microstructures." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **167**, 054506 (2020).
8. H. Mendoza, S. A. Roberts, V. E. Brunini, and A. M. Grillet, "Mechanical and electrochemical response of a LiCo₂ cathode using reconstructed microstructures." *Electrochim. Acta*, **190**, 1 (2016).
9. T. Hutzenlaub, S. Thiele, R. Zengerle, and C. Ziegler, "Three-dimensional reconstruction of a LiCo₂ Li-Ion battery cathode." *Electrochemical and Solid State Letters*, **15**, A33 (2011).
10. G. Li and C. W. Monroe, "Multiscale lithium-battery modeling from materials to cells." *Annu. Rev. Chem. Biomol. Eng.*, **11**, 277 (2020).
11. D. Grazioli, M. Magri, and A. Salvadori, "Computational modeling of Li-ion batteries." *Comput. Mech.*, **58**, 889 (2016).
12. J. S. Newman and K. E. Thomas-Alyea, *Electrochemical Systems. In Electrochemical Systems* (Wiley, Hoboken, N.J.) (2004).
13. M. Doyle, T. F. Fuller, and J. Newman, "The importance of the lithium ion transference number in lithium/polymer cells." *Electrochim. Acta*, **39**, 2073 (1994).
14. M. Doyle, T. F. Fuller, and J. Newman, "Modeling of galvanostatic charge and discharge of the lithium/polymer/insertion cell." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **140**, 1526 (1993).
15. T. F. Fuller, M. Doyle, and J. Newman, "Simulation and optimization of the dual lithium ion insertion cell." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **141**, 1 (1994).
16. A. Salvadori, D. Grazioli, M. Magri, M. G. D. Geers, D. Danilov, and P. H. L. Notten, "On the role of saturation in modeling ionic transport in the electrolyte of (lithium ion) batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **294**, 696 (2015).
17. M. Schmuck and M. Z. Bazant, "Homogenization of the poisson-nernst-planck equations for ion transport in charged porous media." *SIAM J. Appl. Math.*, **75**, 1369 (2015).
18. J. Newman and N. P. Balsara, *Electrochemical Systems* (Wiley, Hoboken, N.J.) 4th ed. (2021).
19. K. M. Diederichsen, E. J. McShane, and B. D. McCloskey, "Promising routes to a high li + transference number electrolyte for lithium ion batteries." *ACS Energy Lett.*, **2**, 2563 (2017).
20. H. K. Kim, N. P. Balsara, and V. Srinivasan, "Continuum description of the role of negative transference numbers on ion motion in polymer electrolytes." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **167**, 110559 (2020).
21. P. Georén and G. Lindbergh, "Characterisation and modelling of the transport properties in lithium battery polymer electrolytes." *Electrochim. Acta*, **47**, 577 (2001).
22. D. M. Pesko, Z. Feng, S. Sawhney, J. Newman, V. Srinivasan, and N. P. Balsara, "Comparing cycling characteristics of symmetric lithium-polymer-lithium cells with theoretical predictions." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **165**, A3186 (2018).
23. S.-L. Wu, A. E. Javier, D. Devaux, N. P. Balsara, and V. Srinivasan, "Discharge characteristics of lithium battery electrodes with a semiconducting polymer studied by continuum modeling and experiment." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **161**, A1836 (2014).
24. D. A. Gribble, L. French, D. B. Shah, J. A. Maslyn, W. S. Loo, K. I. S. Mongcopa, D. M. Pesko, and N. P. Balsara, "Comparing experimental measurements of limiting current in polymer electrolytes with theoretical predictions." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **166**, A3228 (2019).
25. D. B. Shah, H. K. Kim, H. Q. Nguyen, V. Srinivasan, and N. P. Balsara, "Comparing measurements of limiting current of electrolytes with theoretical predictions up to the solubility limit." *J. Phys. Chem. C*, **123**, 23872 (2019).
26. H. Lundgren, M. Behm, and G. Lindbergh, "Electrochemical characterization and temperature dependency of mass-transport properties of lipf6 in ec:dec." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **162**, a413 (2014).
27. J. Landesfeind and H. A. Gasteiger, "Temperature and concentration dependence of the ionic transport properties of lithium-ion battery electrolytes." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **166**, A3079 (2019).
28. T. Hou and C. W. Monroe, "Composition-dependent thermodynamic and mass-transport characterization of lithium hexafluorophosphate in propylene carbonate." *Electrochim. Acta*, **332**, 135085 (2020).
29. P. Georén and G. Lindbergh, "Characterisation and modelling of the transport properties in lithium battery gel electrolytes: part i. the binary electrolyte PC/LiClO₄." *Electrochim. Acta*, **49**, 3497 (2004).
30. A. Nyman, M. Behm, and G. Lindbergh, "Electrochemical characterisation and modelling of the mass transport phenomena in LiPF₆-EC-EMC electrolyte." *Electrochim. Acta*, **53**, 6356 (2008).
31. L. O. Valþen and J. N. Reimers, "Transport properties of LiPF₆-Based Li-Ion battery electrolytes." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **152**, A882 (2005).
32. A. Ehrl, J. Landesfeind, W. A. Wall, and H. A. Gasteiger, "Determination of transport parameters in liquid binary lithium ion battery electrolytes." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **164**, A826 (2017).
33. A. Ehrl, J. Landesfeind, W. A. Wall, and H. A. Gasteiger, "Determination of transport parameters in liquid binary electrolytes: part ii. transference number." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **164**, A2716 (2017).
34. J. Landesfeind, A. Ehrl, M. Graf, W. A. Wall, and H. A. Gasteiger, "Direct electrochemical determination of thermodynamic factors in aprotic binary electrolytes." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **163**, A1254 (2016).
35. S. A. Krachkovskiy, A. D. Pauric, I. C. Halalay, G. R. Goward, and N. M. R. Slice-Selective, "Diffusion measurements: a robust and reliable tool for in situ characterization of ion-transport properties in lithium-ion battery electrolytes." *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.*, **4**, 3940 (2013).
36. A. K. Sethurajan, S. A. Krachkovskiy, I. C. Halalay, G. R. Goward, and B. Protas, "Accurate characterization of ion transport properties in binary symmetric electrolytes using in situ nmr imaging and inverse modeling." *J. Phys. Chem. B*, **119**, 12238 (2015).
37. A. K. Sethurajan, J. M. Foster, G. Richardson, S. A. Krachkovskiy, J. D. Bazak, G. R. Goward, and B. Protas, "Incorporating dendrite growth into continuum models of electrolytes: insights from nmr measurements and inverse modeling." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **166**, A1591 (2019).
38. M. Klett, M. Giesecke, A. Nyman, F. Hallberg, R. W. Lindström, G. Lindbergh, and I. Furó, "Quantifying mass transport during polarization in a li ion battery electrolyte by in Situ 7Li NMR imaging." *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **134**, 14654 (2012).
39. M. Gouverneur, F. Schmidt, and M. Schnhoff, "Negative effective li transference numbers in Li salt/ionic liquid mixtures: does Li drift in the wrong direction ?" *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, **20**, 7470 (2018).
40. D. M. Pesko, K. Timachova, R. Bhattacharya, M. C. Smith, I. Villaluenga, J. Newman, and N. P. Balsara, "Negative transference numbers in poly(ethylene oxide)-based electrolytes." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **164**, E3569 (2017).
41. C. Takacs et al., "Concentration and velocity profiles in a polymeric lithium-ion battery electrolyte." *Energy Environ. Sci.*, **13**, 4312 (2020).
42. P. G. Bruce, J. Evans, and C. A. Vincent, "Conductivity and Transference number measurements on polymer electrolytes." *Solid State Ion.*, **28**, 918 (1988).
43. W. Gorecki, M. Jeannin, E. Belorizky, C. Roux, and M. Armand, "Physical properties of solid polymer electrolyte peo(litfsi) complexes." *J. Phys. Condens. Matter*, **7**, 6823 (1995).
44. K. Pożyczka, M. Marzantowicz, J. R. Dygas, and F. Krok, "Ionic conductivity and lithium transference number of poly(ethylene oxide): litfsi system." *Electrochim. Acta*, **227**, 127 (2017).
45. M. P. Rosenwinkel and M. Schönhoff, "Lithium transference numbers in peo/litfsa electrolytes determined by electrophoretic NMR." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **166**, A1977 (2019).
46. L. H. J. Rajimakers, D. L. Danilov, R. A. Eichel, and P. H. L. Notten, "An advanced all-solid-state li-ion battery model." *Electrochim. Acta*, **330**, 135147 (2020).
47. S. D. Fabre, D. Guy-Bouyssou, P. Bouillon, F. Le Cras, and C. Delacourt, "Charge/discharge simulation of an all-solid-state thin-film battery using a one-dimensional model." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **159**, A104 (2011).
48. A. Bates, S. Mukherjee, N. Schuppert, B. Son, J. G. Kim, and S. Park, "Modeling and simulation of 2D lithium-ion solid state battery." *Int. J. Energy Res.*, **39**, 1505 (2015).
49. N. Wolff, F. Röder, and U. Krewer, "Model based assessment of performance of lithium-ion batteries using single ion conducting electrolytes." *Electrochim. Acta*, **284**, 639 (2018).
50. N. Legrand, S. Raël, B. Knosp, M. Hinaje, P. Desprez, and F. Lapique, "Including double-layer capacitance in lithium-ion battery mathematical models." *J. Power Sources*, **251**, 370 (2014).
51. M. Mykhaylov, M. Ganser, M. Klinsmann, F. E. Hildebrand, I. Guz, and R. M. McMeeking, "An elementary 1-dimensional model for a solid state lithium-ion battery with a single ion conductor electrolyte and a lithium metal negative electrode." *J. MEC. PHYS. SOLIDS*, **123**, 207 (2019).
52. A. Salvadori, D. Grazioli, M. G. D. Geers, D. Danilov, and P. H. L. Notten, "A multiscale-compatible approach in modeling ionic transport in the electrolyte of (lithium ion) batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **293**, 892 (2015).
53. A. A. Franco, A. Rucci, D. Brandell, C. Frayret, M. Gabersek, P. Jankowski, and P. Johansson, "Boosting rechargeable batteries r&d by multiscale modeling: myth or reality?" *Chem. Rev.*, **119**, 4569 (2019).
54. M. Ganser, F. E. Hildebrand, M. Kamlah, and R. M. McMeeking, "A finite strain electro-chemo-mechanical theory for ion transport with application to binary solid electrolytes." *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, **125**, 681 (2019).
55. D. Danilov, R. A. H. Niessen, and P. H. L. Notten, "Modeling all-solid-state li-ion batteries." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **158**, A215 (2011).
56. D. Grazioli, O. Verners, V. Zadin, D. Brandell, and A. Simone, "Electrochemical-mechanical modeling of solid polymer electrolytes: impact of mechanical stresses on li-ion battery performance." *Electrochim. Acta*, **296**, 1122 (2019).
57. M. Landstorfer, S. Funken, and T. Jacob, "An Advanced model framework for solid electrolyte intercalation batteries." *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, **13**, 12817 (2011).
58. Y. Zhao, P. Stein, Y. Bai, M. Al-Siraj, Y. Yang, and B.-X. Xu, "A review on modeling of electro-chemo-mechanics in lithium-ion batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **413**, 259 (2019).
59. S. Inceoglu, A. A. Rojas, D. Devaux, X. C. Chen, G. M. Stone, and N. P. Balsara, "Morphology-conductivity relationship of single-ion-conducting block copolymer electrolytes for lithium batteries." *ACS Macro Lett.*, **3**, 510 (2014).
60. X. Ke, Y. Wang, G. Ren, and C. Yuan, "Towards rational mechanical design of inorganic solid electrolytes for all-solid-state lithium ion batteries." *Energy Storage Mater.*, **26**, 313 (2019).
61. C. Zheng et al., "Interfacial reactions in inorganic all-solid-state lithium batteries." *Batteries & Supercaps*, **4**, 8 (2021).
62. T. Famprikis, P. Canepa, J. Dawson, and C. Masquelier, "Fundamentals of inorganic solid-state electrolytes for batteries." *Nat. Mater.*, **18**, 1278 (2019).
63. H. Zhang, C. Li, M. Piszcz, E. Coya, T. Rojo, L. M. Rodriguez-Martinez, M. Armand, and Z. Zhou, "Single lithium-ion conducting solid polymer electrolytes: advances and perspectives." *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, **46**, 797 (2017).
64. R. Bouchet et al., "Triblock copolymers as highly efficient electrolytes for lithium-metal batteries." *Nat. Mater.*, **12**, 452 (2013).
65. F. Croce, S. Sacchetti, and B. Scrosati, "Advanced, lithium batteries based on high-performance composite polymer electrolytes." *J. Power Sources*, **162**, 685 (2006).

66. Q. Ma et al., "Single lithium-ion conducting polymer electrolytes based on a super-delocalized polyanion." *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **55**, 2521 (2016).
67. M. Piszcz, O. Garcia-Calvo, U. Oteo, J. M. Lopez Del Amo, C. Li, L. M. Rodriguez-Martinez, H. B. Youcef, N. Lago, J. Thielen, and M. Armand, "New single ion conducting blend based on PEO and PA-LITFSI." *Electrochim. Acta*, **255**, 48 (2017).
68. S. Zugmann, M. Fleischmann, M. Amereller, R. M. Gschwind, H. D. Wiemhöfer, and H. J. Gores, "Measurement of transference numbers for lithium ion electrolytes via four different methods, a comparative study." *Electrochim. Acta*, **56**, 3926 (2011).
69. S.-T. Hsu, B. T. Tran, R. Subramani, H. T. T. Nguyen, A. Rajamani, M.-Y. Lee, S.-S. Hou, Y.-L. Lee, and H. Teng, "Free-standing polymer electrolyte for all-solid-state lithium batteries operated at room temperature." *J. Power Sources*, **449**, 227518 (2020).
70. H. Yuan, J. Luan, Z. Yang, J. Zhang, Y. Wu, Z. Lu, and H. Liu, "Single lithium-ion conducting solid polymer electrolyte with superior electrochemical stability and interfacial compatibility for solid-state lithium metal batteries." *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, **12**, 7249 (2020).
71. Q. Zhou, Q. Li, S. Liu, X. Yin, B. Huang, and M. Sheng, "High Li-Ion conductive composite polymer electrolytes for all-solid-state Li-metal batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **482**, 228929 (2021).
72. B. Zhang, Y. Liu, J. Liu, L. Sun, L. Cong, F. Fu, A. Mauger, C. M. Julien, H. Xie, and X. Pan, "Polymer-in-ceramic" based poly(ϵ -caprolactone)/ceramic composite electrolyte for all-solid-state batteries." *J. Energy Chem.*, **52**, 318 (2021).
73. X. Chen and P. M. Vereecken, "Solid and solid-like composite electrolyte for lithium ion batteries: engineering the ion conductivity at interfaces." *Adv. Mater. Interfaces*, **6**, 1800899 (2019).
74. M. Falco, L. Castro, J. R. Nair, F. Bella, F. Bardé, G. Meligrana, and C. Gerbaldi, "UV-cross-linked composite polymer electrolyte for high-rate, ambient temperature lithium batteries." *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.*, **2**, 1600 (2019).
75. Z. Xie, Z. Wu, X. An, X. Yue, P. Xiaokaiti, A. Yoshida, A. Abudula, and G. Guan, "A sandwich-type composite polymer electrolyte for all-solid-state lithium metal batteries with high areal capacity and cycling stability." *J. Membr. Sci.*, **596**, 117739 (2020).
76. H. Huo, Y. Chen, J. Luo, X. Yang, X. Guo, and X. Sun, "Rational design of hierarchical 'ceramic-in-polymer' and 'polymer-in-ceramic' electrolytes for dendrite-free solid-state batteries." *Adv. Energy Mater.*, **9**, 1804004.
77. R. Murugan, V. Thangadurai, and W. Weppner, "Fast lithium ion conduction in garnet-type $\text{Li}_7\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_{12}$." *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **46**, 7778 (2007).
78. P. G. Bruce, "The A-C conductivity of polycrystalline licon, $\text{Li}[\text{sub } 2 + 2_x]\text{Zn}[\text{sub } 1-x]\text{GeO}[\text{sub } 4]$, and a model for intergranular constriction resistances." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **130**, 662 (1983).
79. Z. Zhang, Y. Huang, H. Gao, J. Huang, C. Li, and P. Liu, "An all-solid-state lithium battery using the $\text{Li}_7\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_{12}$ and $\text{Li}_{6.7}\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_{1.7}\text{Ta}_{0.3}\text{O}_{12}$ ceramic enhanced polyethylene oxide electrolytes with superior electrochemical performance." *Ceram. Int.*, **46**, 11397 (2020).
80. X. Peng, K. Huang, S. Song, F. Wu, Y. Xiang, and X. Zhang, "Garnet-polymer composite electrolytes with high Li⁺ conductivity and transference number via well-fused grain boundaries in microporous frameworks." *ChemElectroChem*, **7**, 2389 (2020).
81. D. T. Hallinan, I. Villaluenga, and N. P. Balsara, "Polymer and composite electrolytes." *MRS Bull.*, **43**, 759 (2018).
82. S. Zhao, Q. Wu, W. Ma, and L. Yang, "Polyethylene oxide-based composites as solid-state polymer electrolytes for lithium metal batteries: a mini review." *Front. Chem.*, **8**, 640 (2020).
83. S. Qian, H. Chen, Z. Wu, D. Li, X. Liu, Y. Tang, and S. Zhang, "Designing ceramic/polymer composite as highly ionic conductive solid-state electrolytes." *Batteries & Supercaps*, **4**, 39 (2021).
84. D. Cai, D. Wang, Y. Chen, S. Zhang, X. Wang, X. Xia, and J. Tu, "A highly ion-conductive three-dimensional LLZAO-PEO/LiTFSI solid electrolyte for high-performance solid-state batteries." *Chem. Eng. J.*, **394**, 12499 (2020).
85. J. Zhang, N. Zhao, M. Zhang, Y. Li, P. K. Chu, X. Guo, Z. Di, X. Wang, and H. Li, "Flexible and ion-conducting membrane electrolytes for solid-state lithium batteries: dispersion of garnet nanoparticles in insulating polyethylene oxide." *Nano Energy*, **28**, 447 (2016).
86. J. Bae, Y. Li, J. Zhang, X. Zhou, F. Zhao, Y. Shi, J. B. Goodenough, and G. Yu, "A 3D nanostructured hydrogel-framework-derived high-performance composite polymer lithium-ion electrolyte." *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **57**, 2096 (2018).
87. N. Wu et al., "Enhanced surface interactions enable fast Li⁺ conduction in oxide/polymer composite electrolyte." *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **59**, 4131 (2020).
88. Y. Li, X. Chen, A. Dolocan, Z. Cui, S. Xin, L. Xue, H. Xu, K. Park, and J. B. Goodenough, "Garnet electrolyte with an ultralow interfacial resistance for Li-metal batteries." *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **140**, 6448 (2018).
89. E. P. Roth and C. J. Orendorff, "How electrolytes influence battery safety." *Interface magazine*, **21**, 45 (2012).
90. L. Li et al., "Asymmetric gel polymer electrolyte with high lithium ion conductivity for dendrite-free lithium metal batteries." *J. Mater. Chem. A*, **8**, 8033 (2020).
91. H.-D. Nguyen, G.-T. Kim, J. Shi, E. Paillard, P. Judeinstein, S. Lyonnard, D. Bresser, and C. Iojoiu, "Nanostructured multi-block copolymer single-ion conductors for safer high-performance lithium batteries." *Energy Environ. Sci.*, **11**, 3298 (2018).
92. H. Oh, K. Xu, H. D. Yoo, D. S. Kim, C. Chanthad, G. Yang, J. Jin, I. A. Ayhan, S. M. Oh, and Q. Wang, "Poly(arylene ether)-based single-ion conductors for lithium-ion batteries." *Chem. Mater.*, **28**, 188 (2016).
93. K. Borzutzki, J. Thienenkamp, M. Diehl, M. Winter, and G. Brunklaus, "Fluorinated polysulfonamide based single ion conducting room temperature applicable gel-type polymer electrolytes for lithium ion batteries." *J. Mater. Chem. A*, **7**, 188 (2019).
94. L. Porcarelli, A. S. Shaplov, F. Bella, J. R. Nair, D. Mecerreyes, and C. Gerbaldi, "Single-ion conducting polymer electrolytes for lithium metal polymer batteries that operate at ambient temperature." *ACS Energy Lett.*, **1**, 678 (2016).
95. Z. Chen, D. Steinle, H.-D. Nguyen, J.-K. Kim, A. Mayer, J. Shi, E. Paillard, C. Iojoiu, S. Passerini, and D. Bresser, "High-energy lithium batteries based on single-ion conducting polymer electrolytes and $\text{Li}[\text{Ni}_{0.8}\text{Co}_{0.1}\text{Mn}_{0.1}]\text{O}_2$ cathodes." *Nano Energy*, **77**, 105129 (2020).
96. H. O. Ford, B. Park, J. Z. Jiang, M. E. Seidler, and J. L. Schaefer, "Enhanced Li⁺ conduction within single-ion conducting polymer gel electrolytes via reduced cation-polymer interaction." *ACS Materials Lett.*, **2**, 272 (2020).
97. K. Deng, S. Wang, S. Ren, D. Han, M. Xiao, and Y. Meng, "Network type sp³ boron-based single-ion conducting polymer electrolytes for lithium ion batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **360**, 98 (2017).
98. J. Zhang, S. Wang, D. Han, M. Xiao, L. Sun, and Y. Meng, "Lithium (4-styrenesulfonyl) (trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide based single-ion polymer electrolyte with superior battery performance." *Energy Storage Mater.*, **24**, 579 (2019).
99. L. Ma, P. Nath, Z. Tu, M. Tikekar, and L. A. Archer, "Highly conductive, sulfonated, uv-cross-linked separators for Li-S Batteries." *Chem. Mater.*, **28**, 5147 (2016).
100. Y. Wang, L. Fu, L. Shi, Z. Wang, J. Zhu, Y. Zhao, and S. Yuan, "Gel polymer electrolyte with high Li⁺ transference number enhancing the cycling stability of lithium anodes." *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, **11**, 5168 (2019).
101. J. Zhou, H. Ji, J. Liu, T. Qian, C. Yan, and A. New, "High ionic conductive gel polymer electrolyte enables highly stable quasi-solid-state lithium sulfur battery." *Energy Storage Mater.*, **22**, 256 (2019).
102. B. Boz, For, H. O. Schaefer, J. L. Salvadori, and A. Porous, "Polymer gel electrolytes influence lithium transference number and cycling in lithium-ion." *Batteries. Electron. Mater.*, **2**, 154 (2021).
103. Z. Du, Y. Su, Y. Qu, L. Zhao, X. Jia, Y. Mo, F. Yu, J. Du, and Y. Chen, "A mechanically robust, biodegradable and high performance cellulose gel membrane as gel polymer electrolyte of lithium-ion battery." *Electrochim. Acta*, **299**, 19 (2019).
104. Y. He, J. Wang, Y. Zhang, S. Huo, D. Zeng, Y. Lu, Z. Liu, D. Wang, and H. Cheng, "Effectively suppressing lithium dendrite growth via an es-LiSPCE single-ion conducting nano fiber membrane." *J. Mater. Chem. A*, **8**, 2518 (2020).
105. Z. Y. Kou, C. J. Liu, C. Miao, P. Mei, X. M. Yan, and W. Xiao, "High-performance gel polymer electrolytes using p(vdf-hfp) doped with appropriate porous carbon powders as the matrix for lithium-ion batteries." *Ionics*, **26**, 1729 (2020).
106. J. Jie, Y. Liu, L. Cong, B. Zhang, W. Lu, X. Zhang, J. Liu, H. Xie, and L. Sun, "High-performance PVDF-HFP based gel polymer electrolyte with a safe solvent in Li metal polymer battery." *J. Energy Chem.*, **49**, 80 (2020).
107. X. Hao, H. Wenren, X. Wang, X. Xia, J. Tu, and A. Gel, "Polymer electrolyte based on PVDF-HFP modified double polymer matrices via ultraviolet polymerization for lithium-sulfur batteries." *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, **558**, 145 (2020).
108. K. Luo, D. Shao, L. Yang, L. Liu, X. Chen, C. Zou, D. Wang, Z. Luo, and X. Wang, "Semi-interpenetrating gel polymer electrolyte based on PVDF-HFP for lithium ion batteries." *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, **138**, 49993 (2021).
109. P. Xu, H. Chen, X. Zhou, and H. Xiang, "Gel polymer electrolyte based on pvdf-hfp matrix composited with rGO-PEG-NH₂ for high-performance lithium ion battery." *J. Membr. Sci.*, **617**, 118660 (2021).
110. L. Zhao, J. Fu, Z. Du, X. Jia, Y. Qu, F. Yu, J. Du, and Y. Chen, "High-strength and flexible cellulose/PEG based gel polymer electrolyte with high performance for lithium ion batteries." *J. Membr. Sci.*, **593**, 117428 (2020).
111. D. Kim, X. Liu, B. Yu, S. Mateti, L. A. O' Dell, Q. Rong, and Y. Chen, "Amine-functionalized boron nitride nanosheets: a new functional additive for robust, flexible ion gel electrolyte with high lithium-ion transference number." *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, **30**, 1910813 (2020).
112. W. Xu, J. Wang, F. Ding, X. Chen, E. Nasybulin, Y. Zhang, and J.-G. Zhang, "Lithium metal anodes for rechargeable batteries." *Energy Environ. Sci.*, **7**, 513 (2014).
113. L. Li, S. Li, and Y. Lu, "Suppression of dendritic lithium growth in lithium metal-based batteries." *Chem. Commun.*, **54**, 6648 (2018).
114. X.-B. Cheng, R. Zhang, C.-Z. Zhao, and Q. Zhang, "Toward safe lithium metal anode in rechargeable batteries: a Review." *Chem. Rev.*, **117**, 10403 (2017).
115. R. Xu, X.-B. Cheng, C. Yan, X.-Q. Zhang, Y. Xiao, C.-Z. Zhao, J.-Q. Huang, and Q. Zhang, "Artificial interphases for highly stable lithium metal anode." *Mater.*, **1**, 317 (2019).
116. D. Bistri, A. Afshar, and C. V Di Leo, "Modeling the chemo-mechanical behavior of all-solid-state batteries: a review." *Meccanica*, **56**, 1523 (2021).
117. Y. Lu, Z. Tu, and L. Archer, "Stable lithium electrodeposition in liquid and nanoporous solid electrolytes." *Nat. Mater.*, **13**, 961 (2014).
118. K. Wen, Y. Wang, S. Chen, X. Wang, S. Zhang, and L. A. Archer, "Solid-liquid electrolyte as a nanoion modulator for dendrite-free lithium anodes." *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, **10**, 20412 (2018).
119. K. Share, A. Westover, M. Li, and C. L. Pint, "Surface engineering of nanomaterials for improved energy storage—a review." *Chem. Eng. Sci.*, **154**, 3 (2016).
120. C.-P. Yang, Y.-X. Yin, S.-F. Zhang, N.-W. Li, and Y.-G. Guo, "Accommodating lithium into 3D current collectors with a submicron skeleton towards long-life lithium metal anodes." *Nat. Commun.*, **6**, 8058 (2015).

121. R. Khurana, J. L. Schaefer, L. A. Archer, and G. W. Coates, "Suppression of Lithium dendrite growth using cross-linked polyethylene/poly(ethylene oxide) electrolytes: a new approach for practical lithium-metal polymer batteries." *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **136**, 7395 (2014).
122. J. Trigueiro, R. Borges, R. Lavall, H. Calado, and G. Silva, "Polymeric nanomaterials as electrolyte and electrodes in supercapacitors." *Nano Res.*, **2**, 733 (2009).
123. C. Monroe and J. Newman, "The Impact of elastic deformation on deposition kinetics at lithium/polymer interfaces." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **152**, A396 (2005).
124. C. Fu, V. Venturi, J. Kim, Z. Ahmad, A. W. Ells, V. Viswanathan, and B. A. Helms, "Universal chemomechanical design rules for solid-ion conductors to prevent dendrite formation in lithium metal batteries." *Nat. Mater.*, **19**, 758 (2020).
125. J. N. Chazalviel, "Electrochemical aspects of the generation of ramified metallic electrode deposits." *Phys. Rev. A*, **42**, 7355 (1990).
126. C. Brissot, M. Rosso, J. N. Chazalviel, and S. Lascaud, "Dendritic growth mechanisms in lithium/polymer cells." *J. Power Sources*, **81**, 925 (1999).
127. M. Rosso, T. Gobron, C. Brissot, J. N. Chazalviel, and S. Lascaud, "Onset of dendritic growth in lithium/polymer cells." *J. Power Sources*, **97**, 804 (2001).
128. M. D. Tikekar, L. A. Archer, and D. L. Koch, "Stabilizing electrodeposition in elastic solid electrolytes containing immobilized anions." *Sci. Adv.*, **2**, e1600320 (2016).
129. D. T. Mukul, C. Snehasis, T. Zhengyuan, and A. A. Lynden, "Design principles for electrolytes and interfaces for stable lithium-metal batteries." *Nat. Energy*, **1**, 1 (2016).
130. Z. Tu, S. Choudhury, M. J. Zachman, S. Wei, K. Zhang, L. F. Kourkoutis, and L. A. Archer, "Designing artificial solid-electrolyte interphases for single-ion and high-efficiency transport in Batteries." *Joule*, **1**, 394 (2017).
131. L. Ma, C. Fu, L. Li, K. S. Mayilvahanan, T. Watkins, B. R. Perdue, K. R. Zavadil, and B. A. Helms, "Nanoporous polymer films with a high cation transference number stabilize lithium metal anodes in light-weight batteries for electrified transportation." *Nano Lett.*, **19**, 1387 (2019).
132. M. J. Baran et al., "Diversity-oriented synthesis of polymers of intrinsic microporosity with explicit solid solvation cages for lithium ions." *Nature*, **592**, 225 (2021).
133. J. Liu et al., "Pathways for practical high-energy long-cycling lithium metal batteries." *Nat. Energy*, **4**, 180 (2019).
134. R. Van Noorden, "The rechargeable revolution: a better battery." *Nature*, **507**, 26 (2014).
135. S. Levine, The goalposts move: The new lithium-ion standard is an astonishing \$60 per kWh. <https://themobilistmedium.com/the-goalposts-move-the-new-lithium-ion-standard-is-an-astonishing-60-per-kwh-7153fa8ec328>.
136. X. Gao, X. Liu, R. He, M. Wang, W. Xie, P. N. Brandon, B. Wu, H. Ling, and S. Yang, "Designed high-performance lithium-ion battery electrodes using a novel hybrid model-data driven approach." *Energy Storage Mater.*, **36**, 435 (2021).
137. N. Oghihara, Y. Itou, T. Sasaki, and Y. Takeuchi, "Impedance spectroscopy characterization of porous electrodes under different electrode thickness using a symmetric cell for high-performance lithium-ion batteries." *J. Phys. Chem. C*, **119**, 4612 (2015).
138. J. Betz, G. Bieker, P. Meister, T. Placke, M. Winter, and R. Schmuch, "Theoretical versus practical energy: a plea for more transparency in the energy calculation of different rechargeable battery systems." *Adv. Energy Mater.*, **9**, 1803170 (2019).
139. M. Wang, J. Li, X. He, H. Wu, and C. Wan, "The effect of local current density on electrode design for lithium-ion batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **207**, 127 (2012).
140. I. V. Thorat, D. E. Stephenson, N. A. Zacharias, K. Zaghbi, J. N. Harb, and D. R. Wheeler, "Quantifying tortuosity in porous li-ion battery materials." *J. Power Sources*, **188**, 592 (2009).
141. M. Barrande, R. Bouchet, and R. Denoyel, "Tortuosity of porous particles." *Anal. Chem.*, **79**, 9115 (2007).
142. L. Holzer, D. Wiedenmann, B. Münch, L. Keller, M. Prestat, P. Gasser, I. Robertson, and B. Grobty, "The influence of constrictivity on the effective transport properties of porous layers in electrolysis and fuel cells." *J. Mater. Sci.*, **48**, 2934 (2013).
143. M. Ender, J. Joos, T. Carraro, and E. Ivers-Tiffée, "Quantitative Characterization of LiFePO₄ cathodes reconstructed by FIB/SEM tomography." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **159**, A972 (2012).
144. S. J. Cooper et al., "Image based modelling of microstructural heterogeneity in LiFePO₄ Electrodes for Li-Ion Batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **247**, 1033 (2014).
145. M. Ebner, D.-W. Chung, R. E. García, and V. Wood, "Tortuosity anisotropy in lithium-ion battery electrodes." *Adv. Energy Mater.*, **4**, 1301278 (2014).
146. M. Ebner and V. Wood, "Tool for tortuosity estimation in lithium ion battery porous electrodes." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **162**, A3064 (2014).
147. J. Landesfeind, J. Hattendorff, A. Ehrl, W. A. Wall, and H. A. Gasteiger, "Tortuosity determination of battery electrodes and separators by impedance spectroscopy." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **163**, A1373 (2016).
148. T. Hutzenlaub, A. Asthana, J. Becker, D. R. Wheeler, R. Zengerle, and S. Thiele, "FIB/SEM-based calculation of tortuosity in a porous LiCoO₂ cathode for a Li-ion battery." *Electrochem. Commun.*, **27**, 77 (2013).
149. F. L. E. Usseglio-Viretta et al., "Resolving the discrepancy in tortuosity factor estimation for li-ion battery electrodes through micro-macro modeling and experiment." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **165**, A3403 (2018).
150. B. Vijayaraghavan, D. R. Ely, Y.-M. Chiang, R. García-García, and R. E. García, "An analytical method to determine tortuosity in rechargeable battery electrodes." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **159**, A548 (2012).
151. P. Alam, T. Byholm, and M. Toivakka, "Calculating tortuosity in quasi-random anisotropic packings." *Nord. Pulp Pap. Res. J.*, **21**, 670 (2006).
152. D. E. Stephenson, B. C. Walker, C. B. Skelton, E. P. Gorzkowski, D. J. Rowenhorst, and D. R. Wheeler, "Modeling 3D microstructure and ion transport in porous Li-Ion battery electrodes." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **158**, A781 (2011).
153. D. Dees, E. Gunen, D. Abraham, A. Jansen, and J. Prakash, "Alternating current impedance electrochemical modeling of lithium-ion positive electrodes." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **152**, A1409 (2005).
154. D. Dees, E. Gunen, D. Abraham, A. Jansen, and J. Prakash, "Electrochemical modeling of lithium-ion positive electrodes during hybrid pulse power characterization tests." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **155**, A603 (2008).
155. K. G. Gallagher, D. W. Dees, A. N. Jansen, D. P. Abraham, and S.-H. Kang, "A volume averaged approach to the numerical modeling of phase-transition intercalation electrodes presented for Li_{0.6}C₆." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **159**, A2029 (2012).
156. J. S. Newman and C. W. Tobias, "Theoretical analysis of current distribution in porous electrodes." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **109**, 1183 (2012).
157. Z. Nie, P. McCormack, H. Z. Bilheux, J. C. Bilheux, J. P. Robinson, J. Nanda, and G. M. Koenig, "Probing lithiation and delithiation of thick sintered lithium-ion battery electrodes with neutron imaging." *J. Power Sources*, **191**, 127 (2019).
158. F. Jiang and P. Peng, "Elucidating the performance limitations of lithium-ion batteries due to species and charge transport through five characteristic parameters." *Sci. Rep.*, **6**, 32639 (2016).
159. K. G. Gallagher et al., "Optimizing areal capacities through understanding the limitations of lithium-ion electrodes." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **163**, A138 (2015).
160. T. D. Tran, J. H. Feikert, R. W. Pekala, and K. Kinoshita, "Rate effect on lithium-ion graphite electrode performance." *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, **26**, 1161 (1996).
161. C. Heubner, A. Nickol, J. Seeba, S. Reuber, N. Junker, M. Wolter, M. Schneider, and A. Michaelis, "Understanding thickness and porosity effects on the electrochemical performance of LiNi_{0.6}Co_{0.2}Mn_{0.2}O₂-based cathodes for high energy li-ion batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **419**, 119 (2019).
162. N. Oghihara, S. Kawachi, C. Okuda, Y. Itou, Y. Takeuchi, and Y. Ukyo, "Theoretical and experimental analysis of porous electrodes for lithium-ion batteries by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy using a symmetric cell." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **159**, A1034 (2012).
163. K. Hayamizu, "Direct relations between ion diffusion constants and ionic conductivity for lithium electrolyte solutions." *Electrochim. Acta*, **254**, 101 (2017).
164. Z. Du, D. L. Wood, C. Daniel, S. Kalnaus, and J. Li, "Understanding limiting factors in thick electrode performance as applied to high energy density li-ion batteries." *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, **47**, 405 (2017).
165. M. Doyle, J. Newman, A. S. Gozdz, C. N. Schmutz, and J.-M. Tarascon, "Comparison of modeling predictions with experimental data from plastic lithium ion cells." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **143**, 1890 (1996).
166. H. Zheng, J. Li, X. Song, G. Liu, V. S. Battaglia, and A. Comprehensive, "Understanding of electrode thickness effects on the electrochemical performances of li-ion battery cathodes." *Electrochim. Acta*, **71**, 258 (2012).
167. W. Mei, H. Chen, J. Sun, and Q. Wang, "The effect of electrode design parameters on battery performance and optimization of electrode thickness based on the electrochemical-thermal coupling model." *Sustain. Energy Fuels*, **3**, 148 (2019).
168. J. Park, S. Hyeon, S. Jeong, and H.-J. Kim, "Performance enhancement of Li-ion battery by laser structuring of thick electrode with low porosity." *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, **70**, 178 (2019).
169. C. Sun, S. Liu, X. Shi, C. Lai, J. Liang, and Y. Chen, "3D printing nanocomposite gel-based thick electrode enabling both high areal capacity and rate performance for lithium-ion battery." *Chem. Eng. J.*, **381**, 122641 (2020).
170. X. Wu, S. Xia, Y. Huang, X. Hu, B. Yuan, S. Chen, Y. Yu, and W. Liu, "High-Performance, low-cost, and dense-structure electrodes with high mass loading for lithium-ion batteries." *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, **29**, 1903961 (2019).
171. Z. Wei, L. Xue, F. Nie, J. Sheng, Q. Shi, and X. Zhao, "Study of Sulfonated polyether ether ketone with pendant lithiated fluorinated sulfonic groups as ion conductive binder in lithium-ion batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **256**, 28 (2014).
172. J.-M. Oh, O. Geiculescu, D. DesMarteau, and S. Creager, "Ionomer binders can improve discharge rate capability in lithium-ion battery cathodes." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **158**, A207 (2010).
173. J. Newman, "Optimization of porosity and thickness of a battery electrode by means of a reaction-zone model." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **142**, 97 (1995).
174. R. Zhao, J. Liu, and J. Gu, "The effects of electrode thickness on the electrochemical and thermal characteristics of lithium ion battery." *Appl. Energy*, **139**, 220 (2015).
175. M. Singh, J. Kaiser, and H. Hahn, "Thick electrodes for high energy lithium ion batteries." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **162**, A1196 (2015).
176. B.-S. Lee, Z. Wu, V. Petrova, X. Xing, H.-D. Lim, H. Liu, and P. Liu, "Analysis of rate-limiting factors in thick electrodes for electric vehicle applications." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **165**, A525 (2018).
177. K. Kisu, S. Aoyagi, H. Nagatomo, E. Iwama, M. T. H. Reid, W. Naoi, and K. Naoi, "Internal resistance mapping preparation to optimize electrode thickness and density using symmetric cell for high-performance lithium-ion batteries and capacitors." *J. Power Sources*, **396**, 207 (2018).
178. J. S. Wang, P. Liu, E. Sherman, M. Verbrugge, and H. Tataria, "Formulation and characterization of ultra-thick electrodes for high energy lithium-ion batteries employing tailored metal foams." *J. Power Sources*, **196**, 8714 (2011).
179. W. Lu, A. Jansen, D. Dees, P. Nelson, N. R. Veselka, and G. Henriksen, "High-energy electrode investigation for plug-in hybrid electric vehicles." *J. Power Sources*, **196**, 1537 (2011).
180. C.-J. Bae, C. K. Erdonmez, J. W. Halloran, and Y.-M. Chiang, "Design of battery electrodes with dual-scale porosity to minimize tortuosity and maximize performance." *Adv. Mater.*, **25**, 1254 (2013).
181. S. J. Cho et al., "Hetero-nanonet rechargeable paper batteries: toward ultrahigh energy density and origami foldability." *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, **25**, 6029 (2015).

182. M. Singh, J. Kaiser, H. Hahn, and A. Systematic, "Study of thick electrodes for high energy lithium ion batteries." *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, **782**, 245 (2016).
183. C. Chen et al., "Highly conductive, lightweight, low-tortuosity carbon frameworks as ultrathick 3d current collectors." *Adv. Energy Mater.*, **7**, 1700595 (2017).
184. J. Wang et al., "Toward high areal energy and power density electrode for li-ion batteries via optimized 3D printing approach." *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, **10**, 39794 (2018).
185. Y. Kuang et al., "Conductive cellulose nanofiber enabled thick electrode for compact and flexible energy storage devices." *Adv. Energy Mater.*, **8**, 1802398 (2018).
186. D. J. Noelle, M. Wang, and Y. Qiao, "Improved safety and mechanical characterizations of thick lithium-ion battery electrodes structured with porous metal current collectors." *J. Power Sources*, **399**, 125 (2018).
187. R. Elango, A. Demortière, V. Andrade, M. Morcrette, and V. Seznec, "Thick binder-free electrodes for li-ion battery fabricated using templating approach and spark plasma sintering reveals high areal capacity." *Adv. Energy Mater.*, **8**, 1703031 (2018).
188. L. J. Deiner, T. Jenkins, A. Powell, T. Howell, and M. Rottmayer, "High capacity rate capable aerosol jet printed li-ion battery cathode." *Adv. Eng. Mater.*, **21**, 1801281 (2019).
189. M. E. Sotomayor, C. d. I. Torre-Gamarra, B. Levenfeld, J.-Y. Sanchez, and A. Varez, G.-T. Kim, A. Varzi, and S. Passerini, "Ultra-thick battery electrodes for high gravimetric and volumetric energy density li-ion batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **437**, 226923 (2019).
190. L. S. Kremer, A. Hoffmann, T. Danner, S. Hein, B. Prifling, D. Westhoff, C. Dreer, A. Latz, V. Schmidt, and M. Wohlfahrt-Mehrens, "Manufacturing process for improved ultra-thick cathodes in high-energy lithium-ion batteries." *Energy Technol.*, **8**, 1900167 (2020).
191. J. Wang, M. Wang, N. Ren, J. Dong, Y. Li, and C. Chen, "High-areal-capacity thick cathode with vertically-aligned micro-channels for advanced lithium ion batteries." *Energy Storage Mater.*, **39**, 287 (2021).
192. J. Park, C. Jeon, W. Kim, S.-J. Bong, S. Jeong, and H.-J. Kim, "Challenges, laser processing and electrochemical characteristics on application of ultra-thick electrode for high-energy lithium-ion battery." *J. Power Sources*, **482**, 228948 (2021).
193. D. Liu et al., "Review of recent development of in situ/operando characterization techniques for lithium battery research." *Adv. Mater.*, **31**, 1806620 (2019).
194. H. Li, S. Guo, and H. Zhou, "In-situ/operando characterization techniques in lithium-ion batteries and beyond." *J. Energy Chem.*, **59**, 191 (2021).
195. S. Krachkovskiy, M. L. Trudeau, and K. Zaghib, "Application of magnetic resonance techniques to the in situ characterization of li-ion batteries: a review." *Materials*, **13**, 1694 (2020).
196. M. G. Boebinger, J. A. Lewis, S. E. Sandoval, and M. T. McDowell, "Understanding transformations in battery materials using in situ and operando experiments: progress and outlook." *ACS Energy Lett.*, **5**, 335 (2020).
197. W. Li, D. M. Lutz, L. Wang, K. J. Takeuchi, A. C. Marschilok, and E. S. Takeuchi, "Peering into batteries: electrochemical insight through in situ and operando methods over multiple length scales." *Joule*, **5**, 77 (2021).
198. S. Hwang and E. A. Stach, "Using In Situ and operando methods to characterize phase changes in charged lithium nickel cobalt aluminum oxide cathode materials." *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.*, **53**, 113002 (2020).
199. A. J. Hott, M. Mohammadi, C. M. Schauerma, M. J. Ganter, and A. Jerschow, "Rechargeable lithium-ion cell state of charge and defect detection by in-situ inside-out magnetic resonance imaging." *Nat. Commun.*, **9**, 1776 (2018).
200. M. Mohammadi and A. Jerschow, "In situ and operando magnetic resonance imaging of electrochemical cells: a perspective." *J. Magn. Reson.*, **308**, 106600 (2019).
201. L. Kong, M. Pecht, X. Hu, G. Gui, and Y. Su, "Computed tomography analysis of li-ion battery case ruptures." *Fire Technol.*, **56**, 2565 (2020).
202. J. A. Lewis et al., "Linking void and interphase evolution to electrochemistry in solid-state batteries using operando x-ray tomography." *Nat. Mater.*, **20**, 503 (2021).
203. H. Fathiannasab, G. Kashkooli, A. Li, T. Zhu, L. Chen, and Z. Three-Dimensional, "Modeling of all-solid-state lithium-ion batteries using synchrotron transmission x-ray microscopy tomography." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **167**, 100558 (2020).
204. X. Zhang, Z. Ju, Y. Zhu, K. J. Takeuchi, E. S. Takeuchi, A. C. Marschilok, and G. Yu, "Multiscale understanding and architecture design of high energy/power lithium-ion battery electrodes." *Adv. Energy Mater.*, **11**, 2000808 (2021).
205. S.-H. Park et al., "High areal capacity battery electrodes enabled by segregated nanotube networks." *Nat. Energy*, **4**, 560 (2019).
206. M. F. El-Kady, Y. Shao, and R. B. Kaner, "Graphene for batteries, supercapacitors and beyond." *Nat. Rev. Mater.*, **1**, 1 (2016).
207. J. Wang, Z. Shen, and M. Yi, "Liquid-exfoliated graphene as highly efficient conductive additives for cathodes in lithium ion batteries." *Carbon*, **153**, 156 (2019).
208. R. Raccichini, A. Varzi, D. Wei, and S. Passerini, "Critical insight into the relentless progression toward graphene and graphene-containing materials for lithium-ion battery anodes." *Adv. Mater.*, **29**, 1603421 (2017).
209. J. Ahn, B. Park, J. Kim, M.-K. Um, J. W. Yi, and J.-K. Yoo, "Multifunctional additives for high-energy-density lithium-ion batteries: improved conductive additive/binder networks and enhanced electrochemical properties." *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, **13**, 19970 (2021).
210. F. Font, B. Protas, G. Richardson, and J. M. Foster, "Binder migration during drying of lithium-ion battery electrodes: modelling and comparison to experiment." *J. Power Sources*, **393**, 177 (2018).
211. Y. Zhu, Z. Ju, X. Zhang, D. M. Lutz, L. M. Housel, Y. Zhou, K. J. Takeuchi, E. S. Takeuchi, A. C. Marschilok, and G. Yu, "Evaporation-induced vertical alignment enabling directional ion transport in a 2D-nanosheet-based battery electrode." *Adv. Mater.*, **32**, 1907941 (2020).
212. H. Ji, L. Zhang, M. T. Pettes, H. Li, S. Chen, L. Shi, R. Piner, and R. S. Ruoff, "Ultrathin graphite foam: a three-dimensional conductive network for battery electrodes." *Nano Lett.*, **12**, 2446 (2012).
213. H. Abe, M. Kubota, M. Nemoto, Y. Masuda, Y. Tanaka, H. Munakata, and K. Kanamura, "High-capacity thick cathode with a porous aluminum current collector for lithium secondary batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **334**, 78 (2016).
214. N. Aguiló-Aguayo, P. Pena Espiñeira, P. Manian, A. Bechtold, and T. Three-Dimensional, "Embroidered current collectors for ultra-thick electrodes in batteries." *RSC Adv.*, **6**, 69685 (2016).
215. K. Evanoff, J. Khan, A. A. Balandin, A. Magasinski, W. J. Ready, T. F. Fuller, and G. Yushin, "Towards ultrathick battery electrodes: aligned carbon nanotube-enabled architecture." *Adv. Mater.*, **24**, 533 (2012).
216. J. S. Sander, R. M. Erb, L. Li, A. Gurijala, and Y. M. Chiang, "High-performance battery electrodes via magnetic templating." *Nat. Energy*, **1**, 1 (2016).
217. D. L. Wood, J. Li, and C. Daniel, "Prospects for reducing the processing cost of lithium ion batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **275**, 234 (2015).
218. Z. Nie, R. Parai, C. Cai, C. Michaelis, J. M. LaManna, D. S. Hussey, D. L. Jacobson, D. Ghosh, and G. M. Koenig, "Pore microstructure impacts on lithium ion transport and rate capability of thick sintered electrodes." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **168**, 60550 (2021).
219. M. Park, X. Zhang, M. Chung, G. B. Less, and A. M. Sastry, "A review of conduction phenomena in li-ion batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **195**, 7904 (2010).
220. M. Mangang, H. J. Seifert, and W. Pflöging, "Influence of laser pulse duration on the electrochemical performance of laser structured LiFePO₄ composite electrodes." *J. Power Sources*, **304**, 24 (2016).
221. W. Pflöging, "A review of laser electrode processing for development and manufacturing of lithium-ion batteries." *Nanophotonics*, **7**, 549 (2018).
222. T. Tsuda, N. Ando, S. Nakamura, Y. Ishihara, N. Hayashi, N. Soma, T. Gunji, T. Tanabe, T. Ohsaka, and F. Matsumoto, "Improvement of high-rate discharging performance of LiFePO₄ cathodes by forming micrometer-sized through-holed electrode structures with a pico-second pulsed laser." *Electrochim. Acta*, **296**, 27 (2019).
223. C. Xu, Q. Li, Q. Wang, X. Kou, H.-T. Fang, and L. Yang, "Femtosecond laser drilled micro-hole arrays in thick and dense 2D nanomaterial electrodes toward high volumetric capacity and rate performance." *J. Power Sources*, **492**, 229638 (2021).
224. W. Pflöging, "Recent progress in laser texturing of battery materials: a review of tuning electrochemical performances, related material development, and prospects for large-scale manufacturing." *Institute of Physics: Int. J. Extreme Manuf.*, 012002 (2020).
225. J. Li, M. C. Leu, R. Panat, and J. Park, "A hybrid three-dimensionally structured electrode for lithium-ion batteries via 3D printing." *Mater. Des.*, **119**, 417 (2017).
226. T.-S. Wei, B. Y. Ahn, J. Grotto, and J. A. Lewis, "3D printing of customized li-ion batteries with thick electrodes." *Adv. Mater.*, **30**, 1703027 (2018).
227. K. Sun, T.-S. Wei, B. Y. Ahn, J. Y. Seo, S. J. Dillon, and J. A. Lewis, "3D printing of interdigitated Li-Ion microbattery architectures." *Adv. Mater.*, **25**, 4539 (2013).
228. M. E. Sotomayor, C. d. I. Torre-Gamarra, W. Bucheli, J. M. Amarilla, A. Varez, B. Levenfeld, and J. Y. Sanchez, "Additive-free Li₄Ti₅O₁₂ thick electrodes for Li-Ion batteries with high electrochemical performance." *J. Mater. Chem. A*, **6**, 5952 (2018).
229. V. M. Orera, M. A. Laguna-Bercero, and A. Miguel Larrea, "Fabrication methods and performance in fuel cell and steam electrolysis operation modes of small tubular solid oxide fuel cell (SOFCs): a review." *Front. Energy Res.*, **2**, 22 (2014).
230. W. Liu, X. Huang, L. Guobao, Z. Wang, H. Huang, L. Zhonghua, R. Xue, and L. Chen, "Electrochemical and x-ray photospectroscopy studies of polytetrafluoroethylene and polyvinylidene fluoride in Li/C batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **68**, 344 (1997).
231. J. Sun, L. Yao, Q.-L. Zhao, J. Huang, R. Song, Z. Ma, L.-H. He, W. Huang, and Y.-M. Hao, "Modification on crystallization of poly(vinylidene fluoride) (pvdf) by solvent extraction of poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) in PVDF/PMMA blends." *Front. Mater. Sci.*, **5**, 388 (2011).
232. T. Placke, V. Siozios, R. Schmitz, S. F. Lux, P. Bieker, C. Colle, H. W. Meyer, S. Passerini, and M. Winter, "Influence of graphite surface modifications on the ratio of basal plane to 'non-basal plane' surface area and on the anode performance in lithium ion batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **200**, 83 (2012).
233. Q. Cheng, R. Yuge, K. Nakahara, N. Tamura, S. Miyamoto, and K. O. H. Etched, "Graphite for fast chargeable lithium-ion batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **284**, 258 (2015).
234. L. Zhang, Z. Liu, G. Cui, and L. Chen, "Biomass-derived materials for electrochemical energy storages." *Prog. Polym. Sci.*, **43**, 136 (2015).
235. Y. Ma, J. Ma, and G. Cui, "Small things make big deal: powerful binders of lithium batteries and post-lithium batteries." *Energy Storage Mater.*, **20**, 146 (2019).
236. L. Yoon Koo, "The effect of active material, conductive additives, and binder in a cathode composite electrode on battery performance." *Energies*, **12**, 658 (2019).
237. H. Y. Liang, X. P. Qiu, S. C. Zhang, W. T. Zhu, and L. Q. Chen, "Study of lithiated nafion ionomer for lithium batteries." *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, **34**, 1211 (2004).
238. K.-F. Chiu, S. H. Su, H.-J. Leu, and Y. S. Chen, "Application of lithiated perfluorosulfonate ionomer binders to enhance high rate capability in LiMn₂O₄ cathodes for lithium ion batteries." *Electrochim. Acta*, **117**, 134 (2014).

239. M. Cheng, L. Li, Y. Chen, X. Guo, and B. Zhong, "A functional binder-sulfonated poly(ether ether ketone) for sulfur cathode of Li-S batteries." *RSC Adv.*, **6**, 77937 (2016).
240. J. Liao, J. Wang, Z. Liu, and Z. Ye, "Polar benzimidazole-containing (sulfonated) poly(arylene ether ketone)s as bifunctional binders for lithium-sulfur battery cathodes with high sulfur loadings." *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.*, **2**, 6732 (2019).
241. Q. Shi, L. Xue, Z. Wei, F. Liu, X. Du, and D. D. DesMarteau, "Improvement in LiFePO₄-Li battery performance via poly(perfluoroalkylsulfonyl)imide (PFSI) based ionene composite binder." *J. Mater. Chem. A*, **1**, 15016 (2013).
242. Q. Pan, W. Zhang, M. Pan, B. Zhang, D. Zeng, Y. Sun, and H. Cheng, "Construction of a lithium ion transport network in cathode with lithiated bis (benzene sulfonyl)imide based single ion polymer ionomers." *J. Power Sources*, **283**, 279 (2015).
243. S. Vadivel and M. Sawangphruk, "Pre-lithiated perfluoro-ionomer as an alternative binder for the state-of-the-art Ni-rich LiNi_{0.8}Co_{0.15}Al_{0.05}O₂ cathode of next-generation lithium-ion batteries." *J. Mater. Chem. A*, **8**, 20714 (2020).
244. T. Mi, Q. Yanchunxiao, and O. Eun-Suok, "Application of a polyacrylate latex to a lithium iron phosphate cathode as a binder material." *Energies*, **14**, 1902 (2021).
245. X. Zhang, X. Ge, Z. Shen, H. Ma, J. Wang, S. Wang, L. Liu, B. Liu, L. Liu, and Y. Zhao, "Green water-based binders for LiFePO₄/C cathode in Li-ion batteries: a comparative study." *New J. Chem.*, **45**, 9846 (2021).
246. D. Bresser, D. Buchholz, A. Moretti, A. Varzi, and S. Passerini, "Alternative binders for sustainable electrochemical energy storage—the transition to aqueous electrode processing and bio-derived polymers." *Energy Environ. Sci.*, **11**, 3096 (2018).
247. C.-Y. Wu and J.-G. Duh, "Ionic Network for Aqueous-Polymer Binders to Enhance the Electrochemical Performance of Li-Ion Batteries." *Electrochim. Acta*, **294**, 22 (2019).
248. L. Ibing, T. Gallasch, P. Schneider, P. Niehoff, A. Hintennach, M. Winter, and F. M. Schappacher, "Towards water based ultra-thick li ion battery electrodes—a binder approach." *J. Power Sources*, **423**, 183 (2019).
249. N. D. Trinh, M. Saulnier, D. Lepage, and S. B. Schougaard, "Conductive polymer film supporting LiFePO₄ as composite cathode for lithium ion batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **221**, 284 (2013).
250. D. Cántora-Juárez, C. Pérez-Vicente, S. Ahmad, and J. L. Tirado, "Improving the cycling performance of LiFePO₄ cathode material by poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) coating." *rsos*, **4**, 26108 (2014).
251. P. R. Das, L. Komsijska, O. Osters, and G. Wittstock, "PEDOT: PSS as a functional binder for cathodes in lithium ion batteries." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **162**, A674 (2015).
252. O. V. Levin, S. N. Eliseeva, E. V. Alekseeva, E. G. Tolstopjatova, and V. V. Kondratiev, "Composite LiFePO₄/poly-3, 4-ethylenedioxythiophene cathode for lithium-ion batteries with low content of non-electroactive components." *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, **10**, 8175 (2015).
253. N. Vicente, M. Haro, D. Cántora-Juárez, C. Pérez-Vicente, J. L. Tirado, S. Ahmad, and G. Garcia-Belmonte, "LiFePO₄ particle conductive composite strategies for improving cathode rate capability." *Electrochim. Acta*, **163**, 323 (2015).
254. S. N. Eliseeva, R. V. Apraksin, E. G. Tolstopjatova, and V. V. Kondratiev, "Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy characterization of lifepo4 cathode material with carboxymethylcellulose and Poly-3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene/poly-styrene sulfonate." *Electrochim. Acta*, **227**, 357 (2017).
255. A. V. Kubarkov, O. A. Drozhzhin, E. A. Karpushkin, K. J. Stevenson, E. V. Antipov, and V. G. Sergeev, "Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene):poly(styrenesulfonic acid)-polymer composites as functional cathode binders for high power LiFePO₄ batteries." *Colloid. Polym. Sci.*, **297**, 475 (2019).
256. I. Aldalur, H. Zhang, M. Piszcz, U. Oteo, L. M. Rodriguez-Martinez, D. Shanmukaraj, T. Rojo, and M. Armand, "Jeffamine® based polymers as highly conductive polymer electrolytes and cathode binder materials for battery application." *J. Power Sources*, **347**, 37 (2017).
257. S. Komaba, N. Yabuuchi, T. Ozeki, K. Okushi, H. Yui, K. Konno, Y. Katayama, and T. Miura, "Functional binders for reversible lithium intercalation into graphite in propylene carbonate and ionic liquid media." *J. Power Sources*, **195**, 6069 (2010).
258. S. Lee, E.-Y. Kim, H. Lee, and E.-S. Oh, "Effects of polymeric binders on electrochemical performances of spinel lithium manganese oxide cathodes in lithium ion batteries." *J. Power Sources*, **269**, 418 (2014).
259. W.-J. Song et al., "Significance of ferroelectric polarization in poly(vinylidene difluoride) binder for high-rate Li-Ion diffusion." *Nano Energy*, **32**, 255 (2017).
260. L. Gong, M. H. T. Nguyen, and E.-S. Oh, "High polar polyacrylonitrile as a potential binder for negative electrodes in lithium ion batteries." *Electrochem. Commun.*, **29**, 45 (2013).
261. C.-H. Tsao, C.-H. Hsu, and P.-L. Kuo, "Ionic conducting and surface active binder of poly(ethylene oxide)-block-poly(acrylonitrile) for high power lithium-ion battery." *Electrochim. Acta*, **196**, 41 (2016).
262. T. Gotoh, K. Matsushima, and K.-I. Kikuchi, "Adsorption of Cu and Mn on covalently cross-linked alginate gel beads." *Chemosphere*, **55**, 57 (2004).
263. A. D. Pasquier, A. Blyr, P. Courjal, D. Larcher, G. Amatucci, B. Gérard, and J. M. Tarascon, "Mechanism for limited 55 °C storage performance of Li_{1.05}Mn_{1.95}O₄ electrodes." *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **146**, 428 (1999).
264. S. Lim, K. Lee, I. Shin, A. Tron, J. Mun, T. Yim, and T.-H. Kim, "Physically cross-linked polymer binder based on poly(acrylic acid) and ion-conducting poly(ethylene glycol-co-benzimidazole) for silicon anodes." *J. Power Sources*, **360**, 585 (2017).